

Contents

1	RO-Crate Metadata Specification 1.3	3
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Walkthrough: An initial RO-Crate	5
2.1.1	Running example	6
2.1.2	JSON-LD preamble	7
2.1.3	RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor	7
2.1.4	RO-Crate Root	7
2.1.5	About cross-references	8
2.1.6	Data entities	9
2.1.7	Contextual entities	10
2.2	HTML preview	10
2.3	Overview of specification	11
3	Terminology	12
3.1	Linked Data conventions	14
4	RO-Crate Structure	14
4.1	Types of RO-Crate	14
4.2	RO-Crate Metadata Document (<code>ro-crate-metadata.json</code>)	15
4.3	Attached RO-Crate Package	16
4.3.1	Payload files and directories	17
4.3.2	RO-Crate Website (<code>ro-crate-preview.html</code> and <code>ro-crate-preview_files/</code>) for Packages	17
4.3.3	Self-describing and self-contained	19
4.4	Detached RO-Crate Package	19
5	RO-Crate Metadata	20
5.1	RO-Crate uses Linked Data principles	20
5.2	Common principles for RO-Crate entities	21
5.3	Base metadata standard: Schema.org	21
5.3.1	Differences from Schema.org	22
5.4	Additional metadata standards	22
5.5	Custom RO-Crate terms	24
5.6	Summary of Coverage	24
5.7	Future coverage	25
5.8	Recommended Identifiers	25
6	Root Data Entity	25
6.1	RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor	25
6.1.1	Finding the Root Data Entity	26
6.1.2	Purpose of Metadata Document	27
6.2	Direct properties of the Root Data Entity	27
6.2.1	Root Data Entity identifier	28
6.3	Minimal example of RO-Crate	28
7	Data Entities	30
7.1	Referencing files and folders from the Root Data Entity	30
7.2	Encoding file paths in <code>@ids</code>	31

7.3	Example <i>Attached RO-Crate Package</i>	31
7.4	Core Metadata for Data Entities	32
7.4.1	File Data Entity	32
7.4.2	Directory Data Entity	33
7.4.3	Web-based Data Entities	34
7.4.4	Data entities in an <i>Attached RO-Crate</i> that are also on the web	36
7.4.5	Directories on the web; dataset distributions	37
7.5	Adding detailed descriptions of File encodings	38
7.6	File format profiles	39
7.7	Referencing other RO-Crates	40
7.7.1	Referencing RO-Crates that have a persistent identifier	40
7.7.2	Determining entity identifier for a referenced RO-Crate	41
7.7.3	Referencing another metadata document	41
7.7.4	Profiles of referenced crates	42
7.7.5	Retrieving an RO-Crate	42
8	Representing Contextual Entities	44
8.1	Contextual vs Data entities	44
8.2	Identifiers for contextual entities	44
8.3	People	45
8.4	Organizations as values	45
8.5	Contact information	46
8.6	Publications via citation property	47
8.7	Publisher	49
8.8	Funding and grants	49
8.9	Licensing, Access control and copyright	50
8.9.1	Metadata license	51
8.10	Extra metadata such as Exif	52
8.11	Places	52
8.12	Subjects & keywords	54
8.13	Time	54
8.14	Thumbnails	54
9	The focus of an RO-Crate	56
9.1	RO-Crates with a “main entity”	56
9.1.1	RO-Crates with a data entity as <code>mainEntity</code>	56
9.1.2	RO-Crates with a contextual entity as <code>mainEntity</code>	56
9.2	RO-Crates which focus on multiple <i>Contextual Entities</i>	57
10	Detailing provenance of entities	60
10.1	Equipment used to create files	60
10.2	Software used to create files	61
10.3	Recording changes to RO-Crates	62
10.4	Digital Library and Repository content	64
11	RO-Crate profiles	65
11.1	Publishing an RO-Crate profile	66
11.2	Declaring conformance of an RO-Crate profile	66
11.3	Profile Crate	67

11.3.1	How to retrieve a Profile Crate	69
11.3.2	What is included in the Profile Crate?	70
12	Workflows and Scripts	79
12.1	Describing scripts and workflows	79
12.2	Workflow Runtime and Programming Language	80
12.3	Workflow diagram/sketch	81
12.4	Complying with Bioschemas Computational Workflow profile	82
12.4.1	Describing inputs and outputs	82
12.5	Complete Workflow Example	83
13	Appendixes	86
13.1	Contents	86
14	APPENDIX: Implementation notes	86
14.1	Programming with JSON-LD	86
14.2	Combining with other packaging schemes	86
14.2.1	ELN examples	86
14.2.2	BagIt examples	87
14.3	Repository-specific identifiers	90
15	APPENDIX: RO-Crate JSON-LD	90
15.1	Describing entities in JSON-LD	92
15.2	RO-Crate JSON-LD Context	92
15.3	RO-Crate JSON-LD Media type	94
15.4	Extending RO-Crate	95
15.5	Adding new or ad hoc vocabulary terms	96
15.5.1	Choosing URIs for ad hoc terms	96
15.5.2	Add local definitions of ad hoc terms	97
15.6	Grouping extensions as an RO-Crate profile	98
16	APPENDIX: Handling relative URI references	99
16.1	Converting from Attached to Detached RO-Crate Package	99
16.2	Converting from Detached to Attached RO-Crate Package	102
16.3	Handling relative URI references when using JSON-LD/RDF tools	103
16.4	Flattening JSON-LD from nested JSON	103
16.5	Expanding/parsing JSON-LD keeping relative referencing	105
16.6	Establishing absolute URI for RO-Crate Root	107
16.7	Finding RO-Crate Root in RDF triple stores	108
16.8	Parsing as RDF with a different RO-Crate Root	109
16.9	Establishing a base URI inside a ZIP file	111
16.10	Relativizing absolute URIs within RO-Crate Root	112
17	APPENDIX: Changelog	114
18	References	117

1 RO-Crate Metadata Specification 1.3

- Permalink: <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3>

- Published: 2026-06-22
- Publisher: researchobject.org community
- Status: Recommendation
- JSON-LD context: <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context>
- This version: <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3>
- Alternate formats: Web pages, single-page HTML, PDF, RO-Crate JSON-LD, RO-Crate HTML
- Previous version: <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2>
- Cite as: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20720080> (this version) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3406497> (any version)
- Editors: Peter Sefton, Stian Soiland-Reyes, Eli Chadwick
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See <https://w3id.org/ro/crate> for further details about RO-Crate.

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The key words MUST, MUST NOT, REQUIRED, SHALL, SHALL NOT, SHOULD, SHOULD NOT, RECOMMENDED, MAY, and OPTIONAL in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC 2119.

2 Introduction

This document specifies a method, known as *RO-Crate* (Research Object Crate), of aggregating and describing data for distribution, re-use, publishing, preservation and archiving. RO-Crates aggregate data into a Dataset, and may describe any resource including files, URI-addressable resources, or use other addressing schemes to locate digital or physical data. Describing resources includes technical metadata such as file sizes and types as well as contextual information including how and where datasets and files were created, how they were collated and collected, who was involved in the process, what equipment and software was used, who funded the work, how to cite it, and crucially, how it may be reused, and by whom.

The core of RO-Crate is a machine-readable linked-data document in JSON-LD format known as an **RO-Crate Metadata Document**. RO-Crate metadata documents can, to a large extent, be created and processed just like any other JSON: knowledge of JSON-LD is not needed, unless extending RO-Crate with additional concepts or combining RO-Crate with other Linked Data technologies.

This section introduces the general RO-Crate concepts through a running example, while the normative sections in the rest of the RO-Crate specification define in more detail these and other concepts using separate examples and recommendations.

2.1 Walkthrough: An initial RO-Crate

In the simplest form, to describe some data on disk, a file named `ro-crate-metadata.json` is placed in a directory alongside a set of files or directories. This `ro-crate-metadata.json` file is known as the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*.

In the example below, a single file `data.csv` is placed with the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* in a directory named `crate1`:

Figure 1: Any folder can be made into an RO-Crate by adding `ro-crate-metadata.json`

The presence of the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file means that `crate1` and its children can now be considered to be an **RO-Crate**.

2.1.1 Running example

In this running example, the content of the *RO Crate Metadata Document* is:

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "."}
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "name": "Example dataset for RO-Crate specification",
      "description": "Official rainfall readings for Katoomba, NSW 2022, Australia",
      "datePublished": "2022-12-01",
      "publisher": {"@id": "https://ror.org/04dkp1p98"},
      "license": {"@id": "http://spdx.org/licenses/CC0-1.0"},
      "hasPart": [
        {"@id": "data.csv"}
      ]
    },
    {
      "@id": "data.csv",
      "@type": "File",
      "name": "Rainfall data for Katoomba, NSW Australia February 2022",
      "encodingFormat": "text/csv",
      "license": {"@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/"}
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://ror.org/04dkp1p98",
      "@type": "Organization",

```

```

    "name": "Bureau of Meteorology",
    "description": "Australian Government Bureau of Meteorology",
    "url": "http://www.bom.gov.au/"
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/",
    "@type": "CreativeWork",
    "name": "CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 AU",
    "description": "Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 Australia"
  }
]
}

```

2.1.2 JSON-LD preamble

The preamble of `@context` and `@graph` are JSON-LD structures that help provide global identifiers to the JSON keys and types used in the rest of the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*. These will largely map to definitions in the schema.org vocabulary, which can be used by RO-Crate extensions to provide additional metadata beyond the RO-Crate specification. It is this feature of JSON-LD that helps make RO-Crate extensible for many different purposes – this is explored further in the appendix on JSON-LD.

However, in the general case it should be sufficient to follow the RO-Crate JSON examples directly without deeper JSON-LD understanding. In short, an *RO-Crate Metadata Document* contains a flat list of *entities* as objects in the `@graph` array. These entities are cross-referenced using `@id` identifiers rather than being deeply nested.

2.1.3 RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor

The first JSON-LD *entity* in our example above has the `@id` `ro-crate-metadata.json`:

```

{
  "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
  "about": {"@id": "./"}
}

```

This required entity, known as the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor*, helps this file self-identify as an *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, which is conforming to (`conformsTo`) the RO-Crate specification version 1.3.

The descriptor also indicates via the `about` property which entity in the `@graph` array is the *RO-Crate Root* dataset – the starting point of this RO-Crate.

2.1.4 RO-Crate Root

We can visualise how the above entity references the **RO-Crate Root** as:

Figure 2: showing RO-Crate Metadata descriptor’s about property pointing at the RO-Crate Root entity with matching @id

By convention, in RO-Crate the @id value of ./ means that this document describes the directory of content in which the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is located, as in the example above. This reference from `ro-crate-metadata.json` is therefore marking the `crate1` directory as being the *RO-Crate Root*. The entity whose @id is the *RO-Crate Root* is called the *Root Data Entity*.

Note: This example is a directory-based RO-Crate stored on disk. If the crate is being served from a Web service, such as a data repository or database where files are not organized in directories, then the @id might be an absolute URI instead of ./ – see section *Root Data Entity* for details.

2.1.5 About cross-references

In an *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, entities are cross-referenced using @id reference objects, rather than using deeply nested JSON objects. In short, this *flattened JSON-LD* style allows any entity to reference any other entity, and RO-Crate consumers to directly find all the descriptions of an entity within a single JSON object. So let’s have a look at the *Root Data Entity ./*:

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "...": "...",
  "hasPart": [ {"@id": "data.csv"} ]
}
```

The *Root Data Entity* always has `@type Dataset`, though it may have more than one type. It has several metadata properties that describe the RO-Crate as a whole, as a collection of resources. The section on the Root Data Entity explores further the required and recommended properties of this entity.

2.1.6 Data entities

A main type of resources collected are *data* – simplifying, we can consider data as any kind of file that can be opened in other programs. These are aggregated by the *Root Data Entity* with the `hasPart` property. In this example we have an array with a single value, a reference to the entity describing the file `data.csv`.

Tip: RO-Crates can also contain *data entities* that are folders and Web resources, as well as non-File-like data like online databases – see the section on data entities for more information.

Figure 3: RO-Crate Root entity referencing the data entity with `@id` identifier `data.csv`

If we now follow the `@id` reference for the corresponding *data entity* JSON block, we see it has `@type` value of `File` and additional metadata such as `encodingFormat`. It is recommended that every entity has a human readable `name`, which as shown in this example, does not need to match the filename/identifier. The `encodingFormat` indicates the media file type so that consumers of the crate can open `data.csv` in an appropriate program.

```
{
  "@id": "data.csv",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Rainfall data for Katoomba, NSW Australia February 2022",
```

```

    "encodingFormat": "text/csv",
    "license": { "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/" }
  },

```

For more information on describing files and directories, including their recommended and required attributes, see the section on data entities.

2.1.7 Contextual entities

Moving back to the RO-Crate *Root Data Entity* (with `@id ./`), the publisher of this Dataset should be indicated using the property `publisher` and using a URI to identify the publishing `Organization`, linking to what is known as a *Contextual Entity* that provides some information about the Organization such as its name and web address.

```

{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "publisher": {"@id": "https://ror.org/04dkp1p98"},
  "...": "..."
}

{
  "@id": "https://ror.org/04dkp1p98",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "name": "Bureau of Meteorology",
  "description": "Australian Government Bureau of Meteorology",
  "url": "http://www.bom.gov.au/"
}

```

You may notice the subtle difference between a *data entity* that is conceptually part of the RO-Crate and is file-like (containing bytes), while this *contextual entity* is a representation of a real-life organization that can't be downloaded: following the URL, we would only get its *description*. The section on contextual entities explores several of the entities that can be added to the RO-Crate to provide it with a **context**, for instance how to link to authors and their affiliations. Simplifying slightly, a *data entity* is referenced from `hasPart` in a `Dataset`, while a *contextual entity* is referenced using any other defined property.

2.2 HTML preview

An RO-Crate can be distributed on disk, in packaged format such as a zip file or disk image, or placed on a static website. In any of these cases, an RO-Crate should have an accompanying HTML version (`ro-crate-preview.html`) designed to be human-readable. The exact contents of the preview may vary but should correspond to the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* content and link to the contained data entities. The preview may be generated automatically from the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* (see RO-Crate tools), or even by hand (equivalent to a README).

Below is a screenshot from the preview of the running example, which was generated using the `ro-crate-html` package:

Example dataset for RO-Crate specification

 [Download all the metadata for Example dataset for RO-Crate specification in JSON-LD format](#)

[Check this crate](#)

Browse files Example dataset for RO-Crate specification

@id	<code>./</code>
name [?]	Example dataset for RO-Crate specification
@type	Dataset
description [?]	Official rainfall readings for Katoomba, NSW 2022, Australia
datePublished [?]	2022-12-01
publisher [?]	Bureau of Meteorology
hasPart [?]	Rainfall data for Katoomba, NSW Australia February 2022
Items that reference this one	
about [?]	ro-crate-metadata.json

Figure 4: RO-Crate preview of the running example.

2.3 Overview of specification

The rest of this specification is structured as follows:

- Terminology defines terms such as *Entity* used in this section and the rest of the specification. You may use this section as a quick-reference, but note that most of these are also covered in detail in separate sections.
- RO-Crate Structure defines further how the `ro-crate-metadata.json` and data files can be organized within an *RO-Crate Root* directory.
- Metadata of the RO-Crate explains the connection to Linked Data principles and how RO-Crate keys are mapped to global identifiers. This is mainly of interest for readers already familiar with JSON-LD or ontologies, or which want to expand RO-Crate metadata keys.
- Root Data Entity defines the entities *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* (`ro-crate-metadata.json`) and *Root Data Entity* (`./`) including their required and recommended properties.
- Data Entities explores further how to describe data, including files, directories and Web references. Metadata such as file formats help inform RO-Crate consumers on which tools may be able to process the data.

- Contextual Entities shows how to describe entities used to annotate other entities, adding **People** and **Organization** referenced from **author**, **publication**, **affiliation** etc. Metadata like licensing, funding, locations and subjects can be described using contextual entities.
- The focus of an RO-Crate describes how an RO-Crate can indicate the most important or central entities within it.
- Provenance of Entities explores how the history of making an entity can be added to the RO-Crate using a series of *actions* – this may include real-world activities and instruments, as well as software executions and modifications to the RO-Crate metadata itself.
 - Subsection Digital Library and Repository content details how records in an existing repository (which may reference files, but also physical objects) can be described and published using RO-Crate.
- Workflows and Scripts explains how computational software and code can be added to an RO-Crate, possibly as part of explaining provenance, but also for providing potential usage and further processing of the data.
- Profiles formalises how a set of RO-Crates can indicate they are conforming to a specific *RO-Crate profile*, which may add additional requirements beyond this general RO-Crate specification. Profiles may add additional terms from `schema.org` and other vocabularies, or require a certain type of data entity used in a particular research domain. Profiles can themselves be expressed as an RO-Crate, which is also explored in this section.
- Appendixes contain more technical references and suggestions for developers, e.g. for deciding on `@id` in JSON-LD or extending RO-Crate terms. The appendix also explores how an RO-Crate can be packaged with BagIt or used as part of a repository.

Throughout the specification you will find references to the keys and types reused from `schema.org` through the JSON-LD context, for instance Dataset, which define many more properties than the ones highlighted by sections like Root Data Entity. The intention is that the RO-Crate specification gives a common minimum of metadata, and that producers of RO-Crates can use additional `schema.org` types and properties as needed. When some patterns emerge from such extensions they can be formalized in a published profile to ensure they are also used consistently.

3 Terminology

RO-Crate: A dataset, which is described in a JSON-LD *RO-Crate Metadata Document*.

RO-Crate Metadata Document: A JSON-LD document that describes the *RO-Crate* with structured data in form of *RO-Crate JSON-LD*. This may be stored in a file-system as an *RO-Crate Metadata File*, served via web site or via an API.

RO-Crate Metadata File: An *RO-Crate Metadata Document* stored in a file named `ro-crate-metadata.json` in the *RO-Crate Root* of an *Attached RO-Crate Package*. See section RO-Crate Metadata Document.

Attached RO-Crate Package: A file system directory which functions as a pack-

aged dataset, indicated by the presence of the *RO-Crate Metadata File*. An *Attached RO-Crate Package* carries a payload of zero or more files. See section Types of RO-Crate.

Detached RO-Crate Package: A stand-alone *RO-Crate Metadata Document* which defines a virtual data package by referencing online materials. A *Detached RO-Crate Package* does not have a payload. See section Types of RO-Crate.

Detached RO-Crate Metadata File: An *RO-Crate Metadata Document* stored in a file named `#{prefix}-ro-crate-metadata.json` or `ro-crate-metadata.json` where `#{prefix}`, if present, is a file-system safe version identifier or name for the RO-Crate.

RO-Crate Root: The top-level directory of an *RO-Crate Package*. See section RO-Crate structure.

RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor: A *Contextual Entity* of type `CreativeWork`, which describes the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* and links it to the *Root Data Entity*. See section RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor

RO-Crate Website: Human-readable HTML pages which describe the RO-Crate (i.e. the *Root Data Entity*, its *Data Entities* and *Context Entities*), with a homepage at `ro-crate-preview.html`. See section RO-Crate Website.

Type: A classification of objects or their descriptions. The type (or “class”) is given as a short-hand *key*, mapped by the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context* to a *URI* that has the type definition. See appendix RO-Crate JSON-LD.

Data Entity: A JSON-LD representation (in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*) of a directory, file, or other Web resource which is considered *contained* by the *RO-Crate*. See section Data entities.

Property: A relationship from one *entity* to another entity, or to a *value*. The type of relationship is identified by a *URI*, mapped to a *key* by *JSON-LD*. See appendix RO-Crate JSON-LD.

Root Data Entity: A *Data Entity* of type `Dataset`, representing the RO-Crate as a whole. See section Root Data Entity.

JSON-LD: A JSON-based file format for storing *Linked Data*. This document assumes JSON-LD 1.0. JSON-LD use a *context* to map from JSON keys to *URIs*. See appendix RO-Crate JSON-LD.

JSON: The *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) Data Interchange Format* as defined by RFC 7159; a structured text file format that can be programmatically consumed and generated in a wide range of programming languages. The main JSON structures are *objects* (`{}`) indexed by *keys*, sequential *arrays* (`[]`) and literal *values* (`""`).

Contextual Entity: A JSON-LD representation of an entity associated with another *Entity*, in order to adequately describe it. For example, a Person, Organization (including research projects), item of equipment (`IndividualProduct`), license or any other *thing* or *event* that forms part of the metadata for a *Data Entity*. *Properties* of contextual entities may refer to further entities. See section Contextual Entities.

Linked Data: A data structure where properties, types and resources are identified with *URIs*, which if retrieved over the Web, further describe or provide the identified property/type/resource.

URI: A *Uniform Resource Identifier* as defined in RFC 3986, for example `http://example.com/path/file.html` - commonly known as *URL*. In this document the term *URI* includes *IRI*, which also permit international Unicode characters. The URI identifies a downloadable resource (e.g. an image) or a concept (e.g. a *type* definition).

URI Path: The relative *path* element of an *URI* as defined in RFC3986 section 3.3, e.g. `path/file.html`

RO-Crate JSON-LD Context: A JSON-LD context that provides Linked Data mapping for RO-Crate metadata to vocabularies like Schema.org. This mapping assigns meaning to the JSON keys, see appendix RO-Crate JSON-LD.

RO-Crate JSON-LD: JSON-LD that use the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context* and contain RO-Crate metadata, written as if flattened and then compacted according to the rules in JSON-LD 1.0. The *RO-Crate JSON-LD* for an *RO-Crate* is stored or transmitted in the `_RO-Crate Metadata Document`.

3.1 Linked Data conventions

Throughout this specification, RDF terms (*properties*, *types*) are referred to using the *keys* defined in the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context*.

Following Schema.org practice, **property** names start with lowercase letters and **Type** names start with uppercase letters.

In the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* the RDF terms use their RO-Crate JSON-LD names as defined in the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context*, which is available at <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context>

4 RO-Crate Structure

4.1 Types of RO-Crate

An *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is used to package data in one of two ways:

1. An *Attached RO-Crate Package* that defines an on-disk collection of data:
 - It is defined within a file-system-like service as a directory (known as the *RO-Crate Root*) with the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* saved in a file-like entity with a file name of `ro-crate-metadata.json`.
 - References to files and directories in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* are present in the RO-Crate or available online as Web-based Data Entities.
 - Typically, software processing an *Attached RO-Crate Package* would be passed a path to a directory or a zip file.
2. A *Detached RO-Crate Package*:
 - Is defined by a stand-alone *RO-Crate Metadata Document* which may be stored in a file or distributed via an API.

- References to files and directories in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* are all Web-based Data Entities.
- If stored in a file, known as a *Detached RO-Crate Metadata File*, the filename SHOULD be `#{prefix}-ro-crate-metadata.json` rather than `ro-crate-metadata.json` where the variable `#{prefix}` is a human readable version of the dataset's ID or name, to signal that on disk, the presence of the file does not indicate an *Attached RO-Crate Data Package*.
- Typically, software processing a *Detached RO-Crate Package* would be passed a path to a file, an absolute URI, or a JSON string or object, without a directory context.

RO-Crate Metadata Documents MAY also be processed in non-packaging contexts by tools such as website generators or crate visualizers, where data entities are not processed, or in applications which use RO-Crate conventions for representing context (such as a schema definition using Schema.org conventions).

Note: Client software may provide modes which force a particular packaging mode to be assumed. For example, if the software is passed a directory, then it would assume that is processing an *Attached RO-Crate Package*. If passed a path to a file, it could work in *Detached RO-Crate Package* mode, and possibly attempt to resolve *Web Based Data Entities*. It could also provide a mode to simply parse the document and process it without referencing or validating Data entities in any special way.

In all crates the metadata is completed with contextual entities that further describe the relationships and context of the data to form a *Research Object*.

4.2 RO-Crate Metadata Document (`ro-crate-metadata.json`)

JSON-LD is a structured form of JSON that can represent a *Linked Data* graph.

- The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* MUST be a document which is valid JSON-LD 1.0 in flattened and compacted form.
- The *RO-Crate JSON-LD* MUST use the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context* <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context> by reference.

The graph MUST describe:

1. The RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor
2. The Root Data Entity
3. Zero or more Data Entities
4. Zero or more Contextual Entities

Any referenced *contextual entities* SHOULD also be described in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* with the same identifier. Similarly any *contextual entity* in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* SHOULD be linked to from at least one of the other entities using the same identifier.

The appendix RO-Crate JSON-LD details the general structure of the JSON-LD that is expected in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*. In short, the rest of this specification describes the different types of entities that can be added as `{}` objects to the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* `@graph` array below:

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [

  ]
}
```

4.3 Attached RO-Crate Package

An **Attached RO-Crate Package** is used to contain and describe an optional *payload* of files and directories as well as web-based data entities along with their contextual information.

When processing an *Attached RO-Crate Package* the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* MUST be present in the *RO-Crate Root* and it MUST be named `ro-crate-metadata.json`.

An *Attached RO-Crate Package* can be stored and published in multiple ways depending on its use:

- On a typical hierarchical *file system* (e.g. `/files/shared/crates/my-crate-01/`)
- Exposed as a *Web resource* within a folder structure (e.g. `https://www.researchobject.org/2021-packaging-research-artefacts-with-ro-crate/`)
- *Packaged* within a ZIP file, BagIt archive or OCFL structure
- *Archived* as a set of named files in other ways (e.g. Zenodo deposit)

A valuable feature of the *Attached RO-Crate Package* approach is that the metadata is preserved when a crate is transferred between these types of storage/publication systems.

The file path structure an *Attached RO-Crate Package* MUST follow is:

```
<RO-Crate root directory>/
| ro-crate-metadata.json # RO-Crate Metadata File containing the RO-Crate Metadata Do
| ro-crate-preview.html # RO-Crate Website homepage MAY be present
| ro-crate-preview_files/ # MAY be present
| | [other RO-Crate Website files]
| [payload files and directories] # 0 or more
```

The name of the *RO-Crate root* directory is not defined, but a root directory is identifiable by the presence of the *RO-Crate Metadata File*, `ro-crate-metadata.json`. For instance, if an *RO-Crate* is archived in a ZIP-file, the ZIP root directory is an *RO-Crate root* directory if it contains `ro-crate-metadata.json`.

The payload files and directories MAY be described within the *RO-Crate Metadata File* as Data Entities. Additional Web-based Data Entities MAY also be described, but are not considered part of the payload.

The `@id` of the *Root Data Entity* in an *Attached RO-Crate Package* MUST be either `./` or be a URI, such as a DOI URL or other persistent URL which is considered to be the main identifier of the *Attached RO-Crate Package*.

Note: Earlier versions of RO-Crate mandated an `@id` of `./` as a convention for identifying the *Root Data Entity*, but the use of the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* means that this is no longer required, freeing-up the *Root Data Entity*

`@id` to be used to indicate what should be considered the canonical URI for an RO-Crate Package. Other mechanisms for specifying the ‘main identifier’ involve multiple JSON-LD entities and may be ambiguous.

4.3.1 Payload files and directories

These are the actual files and directories that make up the **payload** of the dataset being described in an *Attached RO-Crate Package*.

The base RO-Crate specification makes no assumptions about the presence of any specific files or folders beyond the reserved RO-Crate files described above.

Payload files may appear directly in the *RO-Crate Root* alongside the *RO-Crate Metadata File*, and/or appear in sub-directories of the *RO-Crate Root*. Each file and directory MAY be represented as Data Entities in the *RO-Crate Metadata File*.

An RO-Crate may also contain Web-based Data Entities that are not present as part of the payload and referenced using absolute URIs. These may require additional preservation measures.

Tip: An RO-Crate packaged with BagIt may reference external files which are not present in the *RO-Crate Root* hierarchy until the BagIt has been *completed*. This method for referencing external files can be used for files that are large, require authentication or otherwise inconvenient to transfer with the RO-Crate, but which should nevertheless still be considered part of the *payload*. RO-Crate has a similar mechanism for referencing such external files using both an `@id` to reference a local path and `contentUrl` property to indicate a source for that data. See the section on File Data Entities.

4.3.2 RO-Crate Website (`ro-crate-preview.html` and `ro-crate-preview_files/`) for Packages

In addition to the machine-oriented *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, an *Attached RO-Crate Package* MAY include a human-readable HTML rendering of the same information, known as the *RO-Crate Website*. If present, the *RO-Crate Website* MUST be a file named `ro-crate-preview.html` in the root directory, which MAY serve as the entry point to other web-resources, which MUST be in `ro-crate-preview_files/` in the root directory.

If present in the root directory of an *Attached RO-Crate Package* as `ro-crate-preview.html` (or otherwise served in a *Detached RO-Crate Package*), the RO-Crate Website MUST:

- Be a valid HTML 5 document
- Be useful to users of the RO-Crate - this will vary by community and intended use, but in general the aim is to assist users in reusing data by explaining what it is, how it was created, how it can be used and how to cite it. One simple approach to this is to expose *all* the metadata in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*.

`ro-crate-preview.html` SHOULD:

- Display at least the metadata relating to the *Root Data Entity* as static HTML without the need for scripting. It MAY contain extra features enabled by JavaScript.
- When a *Data Entity* or *Contextual Entity* is referenced by its ID:
 - If it has a name property, provide a link to its HTML version.
 - If it does not have a name (e.g. a GeoCoordinates location), show it embedded in the HTML for the entity.
 - For external URI values, provide a link.
- For keys that resolve in the RO-Crate JSON-LD Context to a URI, indicate this (the simplest way is to link the key to its definition).
- If there are additional resources necessary to render the preview (e.g. CSS, JSON, HTML), link to them in a subdirectory `ro-crate-preview_files/`

Note: Previous versions of the Specification recommended that the *RO-Crate Website* should contain a redundant copy of the RO-Crate Metadata Document, but there is no evidence that this has been useful and it is no longer recommended.

The *RO-Crate Website* is not considered a part of the RO-Crate payload in an *Attached RO-Crate Package*, but serves as a way to make metadata available in a user-appropriate format. The `ro-crate-preview.html` file and the `ro-crate-preview_files/` directory and any contents SHOULD NOT be included in the `hasPart` property of the *Root Dataset* or any other *Dataset* entity within an RO-Crate.

Metadata about parts of the *RO-Crate Website* MAY be included in an RO-Crate as in the following example. Metadata such as an `author` property, `dateCreated` or other provenance can be included, including details about the software that created them, as described in Software used to create files.

```
{
  "@id": "ro-crate-preview.html",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "about": {"@id": "."}
}

{
  "@id": "https://www.npmjs.com/package/ro-crate-html-js",
  "@type": "SoftwareApplication",
  "url": "https://www.npmjs.com/package/ro-crate-html-js",
  "name": "ro-crate-html-js",
  "version": "1.4.19"
}

{
  "@id": "#ro-crate-preview-generation",
  "@type": "CreateAction",
  "name": "Create HTML summary",
  "endTime": "2022-10-019T17:01:07+10:00",
  "instrument": {
    "@id": "https://www.npmjs.com/package/ro-crate-html-js"
  },
}
```

```

    "object": {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json"
    },
    "result": {
      "@id": "ro-crate-preview.html"
    }
  }
}

```

4.3.3 Self-describing and self-contained

Attached RO-Crates Packages SHOULD be self-describing and self-contained.

A minimal *Attached RO-Crate Package* is a directory containing a single *RO-Crate Metadata Document* stored as an RO-Crate Metadata File `ro-crate-metadata.json`.

At the basic level, an *Attached RO-Crate Package* is a collection of files and resources represented as a Schema.org Dataset, that together form a meaningful unit for the purposes of communication, citation, distribution, preservation, etc. The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* describes the RO-Crate, and MUST be stored in the *RO-Crate Root*.

While RO-Crate is well catered for describing a *Dataset* as files and relevant metadata that are *contained* by the RO-Crate in the sense of living within the same root directory, RO-Crates can also reference external resources which are stored or accessed separately, via absolute URIs. This is particularly recommended where some resources cannot be co-hosted for practical or legal reasons, or if the RO-Crate itself is primarily web-based.

It is important to note that the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is **not necessarily an exhaustive manifest** or inventory, that is, it is not required to list or describe all files in the package. Rather it is focused on providing sufficient amount of metadata to understand and use the content, and is designed to be compatible with existing and future approaches that *do* have full inventories / manifest and integrity checks, e.g. by using checksums, such as BagIt and Oxford Common File Layout OCFL Objects.

The intention is that RO-Crates can work well with a variety of archive file formats, e.g. tar, zip, etc., and approaches to capturing file manifests and file fixity, such as BagIt, OCFL and git (see also appendix Combining with other packaging schemes). An RO-Crate can also be hosted on the web or mainly refer to web resources, although extra care to ensure persistence and consistency should be taken for archiving such RO-Crates.

4.4 Detached RO-Crate Package

A *Detached RO-Crate Package* is an RO-Crate, defined in an *RO-Crate Metadata Document* without a defined root directory, where the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* content is accessed independently (e.g. as part of a programmatic API).

Unlike an *Attached RO-Crate Package*, a *Detached RO-Crate Package* is not processed in a file-system context and thus does not carry a data *payload* in the

same sense, but may reference data deposited separately, or purely reference contextual entities.

In a *Detached RO-Crate Package* the root data entity SHOULD have an @id which is an absolute URL if it is available online. If it is not yet, or will never be available online then @id MAY be any valid URI - including ./.

Any data entities in a *Detached RO-Crate Package* MUST be Web-based Data Entities.

A Detached RO-Crate Package may still use #-based local identifiers for contextual entities.

The concept of an *RO-Crate Website* is undefined for a *Detached RO-Crate Package*.

To distribute a *Detached RO-Crate Package* and optionally to provide an RO-Crate Website, any *Detached RO-Crate Package* can be saved in a directory (and zipped or otherwise bundled) and will function as an *Attached RO-Crate Package* with no payload data. See the appendix on converting from Detached to Attached RO-Crate Package for further guidance on this.

5 RO-Crate Metadata

RO-Crate aims to capture and describe the Research Object using structured *metadata*. Specifically, an RO-Crate is described using *JSON-LD* by an *RO-Crate Metadata Document*. As explained in section RO-Crate Structure this may be stored in an *RO-Crate Metadata File*.

The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* contains the metadata that describes the RO-Crate and its content, in particular:

- Root Data Entity - the RO-Crate **Dataset** itself, a gathering of data
- Data Entities - the *data* payload, in the form of files and folders
- Contextual Entities - related things in the world (e.g. people, organizations, places), providing provenance for the data entities and the RO-Crate.

This machine-readable metadata can also be represented for human consumption in the *RO-Crate Website*, linking to data and Web resources.

5.1 RO-Crate uses Linked Data principles

RO-Crate makes use of the Linked Data principles for its description. In particular:

1. (Meta)data should be made available as **Open Data** on the web.
2. (Meta)data should be **machine-readable** in a structured format.
3. (Meta)data should *not* require proprietary software packages.
4. (Meta)data should use open standards from W3C, such as RDF and SPARQL.
5. (Meta)data should **link** to other people's data to provide context, using *URIs* as global identifiers

RO-Crate realizes these principles using a particular set of technologies and best practices:

1. The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* can be stored in an *RO-Crate Metadata File*. The *RO-Crate Metadata File* and an *RO-Crate Website* can be directly published on the web together with the RO-Crate payload. In addition, a data package (e.g. BagIt Zip archive) that contains the RO-Crate can also be published on the web.
2. The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is based on the structured data format JSON-LD.
3. Multiple open source tools/libraries are available for JSON and for JSON-LD.
4. The *RO-Crate Website* is HTML 5, and the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is JSON-LD, one of the W3C RDF 1.1 formats.
5. The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* reuses common vocabularies like Schema.org, and this specification recommends identifiers it should link to.

5.2 Common principles for RO-Crate entities

For all entities listed in an *RO-Crate Metadata Document* the following principles apply:

1. The entity **MUST** have an `@id` (see Describing entities in JSON-LD).
2. The entity **MUST** have a `@type`, which **MAY** be an array.
3. The `@type` **SHOULD** include at least one Schema.org type that accurately describes the entity. Thing or CreativeWork are valid fallbacks if no alternative external or ad-hoc term is found (see Extending RO-Crate).
4. The entity **SHOULD** have a human-readable `name`, in particular if its `@id` does not go to a human-readable Web page.
5. The properties used on the entity **SHOULD** be applicable to the `@type` (or superclass) according to their definitions. For instance, the property `publisher` can be used on a Dataset as it applies to its superclass CreativeWork.
6. Property references to other entities (e.g. `author` property to a Person entity) **MUST** use the `{ "@id": "..."}` object form (see JSON-LD appendix).
7. The entity **SHOULD** be ultimately referenceable from the root data entity (possibly through another reachable data entity or contextual entity).

5.3 Base metadata standard: Schema.org

Schema.org is the base metadata standard for RO-Crate. Schema.org was chosen because it is widely used on the World Wide Web and supported by search engines, on the assumption that discovery is likely to be maximized if search engines index the content.

Note: As far as we know there is no alternative, well-maintained linked-data schema for research data with the coverage needed for this project - i.e. a single standard for expressing all the examples presented in this specification.

RO-Crate relies heavily on Schema.org, using a constrained subset of JSON-LD,

and this specification gives opinionated recommendations on how to represent the metadata using existing linked data best practices.

Tip: The main principle of RO-Crate is to use a Schema.org term whenever possible, even if its official definition may seem broad or related to every day objects. For instance, `IndividualProduct` can describe scientific equipment and instruments (see Provenance of entities). RO-Crate implementers are free to use additional properties and types beyond this specification (see also appendix Extending RO-Crate).

5.3.1 Differences from Schema.org

Generally, the standard *type* and *property* names (*terms*) from Schema.org should be used. However, RO-Crate uses variant names for some elements, specifically:

- `File` is mapped to `http://schema.org/MediaObject` which was chosen as a compromise as it has many of the properties that are needed to describe a generic file. Future versions of Schema.org or a research data extension may re-define `File`.
- `Journal` is mapped to `http://schema.org/Periodical`.

Warning :JSON-LD examples given on the Schema.org website might not be in *flattened* form, but *RO-Crate JSON-LD* is flattened; any nested entities in *RO-Crate JSON-LD* MUST be described as separate contextual entities in the flat `@graph` list.

To simplify processing and avoid confusion with string values, the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context* requires URIs and entity references to be given in the form `"author": {"@id": "http://example.com/alice"}`, even where Schema.org for some properties otherwise permit shorter forms like `"author": "http://example.com/alice"`.

See the appendix RO-Crate JSON-LD for details.

5.4 Additional metadata standards

RO-Crate also uses the *Portland Common Data Model* (PCDM version `https://pcdm.org/2016/04/18/models`) to describe repositories or collections of digital objects and imports these terms:

- `RepositoryObject` mapped to `http://pcdm.org/models#Object`
- `RepositoryCollection` mapped to `http://pcdm.org/models#Collection`
- `RepositoryFile` mapped to `http://pcdm.org/models#File`
- `hasMember` mapped to `http://pcdm.org/models#hasMember`
- `hasFile` mapped to `http://pcdm.org/models#hasFile`

Note: The terms `RepositoryObject` and `RepositoryCollection` are renamed to avoid collision between other vocabularies and the PCDM terms `Collection` and `Object`. The term `RepositoryFile` is renamed to avoid clash with RO-Crate's `File` mapping to `http://schema.org/MediaObject`.

RO-Crate uses the Profiles Vocabulary to describe profiles using these terms and definitions:

- **ResourceDescriptor** mapped to <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/ResourceDescriptor> (definition)
- **ResourceRole** mapped to <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/ResourceRole> (definition)
- **Profile** mapped to <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/Profile> (definition)
- **hasArtifact** mapped to <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/hasArtifact> (definition)
- **hasResource** mapped to <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/hasResource> (definition)
- **hasRole** mapped to <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/hasRole> (definition)

From Dublin Core Terms RO-Crate uses:

- **conformsTo** mapped to <http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo>
- **Standard** mapped to <http://purl.org/dc/terms/Standard>

From the IANA link relations registry:

- **cite-as** mapped to <http://www.iana.org/assignments/relation/cite-as> (defined by RFC8574)

These terms are being proposed by Bioschemas profile ComputationalWorkflow 1.0-RELEASE and FormalParameter 1.0-RELEASE to be integrated into Schema.org:

- **ComputationalWorkflow** mapped to <https://bioschemas.org/terms/ComputationalWorkflow>
- **FormalParameter** mapped to <https://bioschemas.org/terms/FormalParameter>
- **input** mapped to <https://bioschemas.org/terms/input>
- **output** mapped to <https://bioschemas.org/terms/output>

Note: In version 1.3 of this specification the proposed Bioschemas terms use the <https://bioschemas.org/terms/> namespace; previous versions 1.1 and 1.2 used the temporary <https://bioschemas.org/> namespace. Future releases of RO-Crate may reflect mapping to the <http://schema.org/> namespace.

To support geometry in Places, these terms from the GeoSPARQL ontology:

- **Geometry** mapped to <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#Geometry>
- **asWKT** mapped to <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT>

From CodeMeta 3.0:

- **buildInstructions** mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/buildInstructions>
- **developmentStatus** mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/developmentStatus>
- **continuousIntegration** mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/continuousIntegration>
- **embargoEndDate** mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/embargoEndDate>
- **hasSourceCode** mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/hasSourceCode>

- `isSourceCodeOf` mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/isSourceCodeOf>
- `issueTracker` mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/issueTracker>
- `readme` mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/readme>
- `referencePublication` mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/referencePublication>
- `softwareSuggestions` mapped to <https://codemeta.github.io/terms/softwareSuggestions>

Warning :As of 2025-01-09, the CodeMeta URIs do not resolve correctly, but are used here to match the Codemeta JSON-LD context <https://w3id.org/codemeta/3.0> (issue #275). The CodeMeta terms `maintainer` and `funding` are not mapped, as these are already defined by schema.org.

5.5 Custom RO-Crate terms

The RO-Crate community maintains a common namespace for terms not covered by other vocabularies. This is mainly used by RO-Crate profiles, but the following term is included in the core RO-Crate context:

- `localPath` mapped to <https://w3id.org/ro/terms#localPath>

5.6 Summary of Coverage

RO-Crate is simply a way to make metadata assertions about a set of files and folders that make up a *Dataset*. These assertions can be made at two levels:

- Assertions at the RO-Crate level: for an RO-Crate to be useful, some metadata should be provided about the dataset as a whole (see minimum requirements for different use-cases below). In the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, we distinguish the *Root Data Entity*, which represents the RO-Crate as a whole, from other *Data Entities* (files and folders contained in the RO-Crate) and *Contextual Entities*, e.g. a person, organisation, place related to an RO-Crate *Data Entity*.
- Assertions about files and folders contained in the RO-Crate: in addition to providing metadata about the RO-Crate as a whole, RO-Crate allows metadata assertions to be made about any other *Data Entity*.

This document has guidelines for ways to represent common requirements for describing data in a research context, e.g.:

- Contact information for a data set.
- Descriptive information for a dataset and the files within it and their contexts such as an abstract, spatial and temporal coverage.
- Associated publications.
- Funding relationships.
- Provenance information of various kinds; who (people and organizations) and what (instruments and computer programs) created or contributed to the data set and individual files within it.
- Workflows that operate on the data using standard workflow descriptions, including ‘single step workflows,’ executable files, or environments such as

Singularity containers or Jupyter notebooks.

However, as RO-Crate uses the Linked Data principles, adopters of RO-Crate are free to supplement RO-Crate using Schema.org metadata and/or assertions using other *Linked Data* vocabularies (see Extending RO-Crate).

5.7 Future coverage

A future version of this specification will aim to cater for variable-level assertions: in some cases, e.g. for tabular data, additional metadata may be provided about the structure and variables within a given file. See the use case Describe a tabular data file directly in RO-Crate metadata for work-in-progress.

5.8 Recommended Identifiers

RO-Crate JSON-LD SHOULD use the following IDs where possible:

- For a *Root Data Entity*, an identifier which is RECOMMENDED to be a `https://doi.org/` URI.
- For a Person participating in the research process: ORCID identifiers, e.g. `https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097`
- For Organizations including funders, Research Organization Registry URIs, e.g. `https://ror.org/0384j8v12`
- For entities of type Place, a geonames URL, e.g. `http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/`
- For file formats, a Pronom URL, for example `https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/831`.

In the absence of the above, RO-Crates SHOULD contain stable persistent URIs to identify all entities wherever possible.

6 Root Data Entity

The **Root Data Entity** is a Dataset that represents the RO-Crate as a whole; a *Research Object* that includes the *Data Entities* and the related *Contextual Entities*.

6.1 RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor

The *RO-Crate Metadata Document* MUST contain a self-describing **RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor** with the `@id` value `ro-crate-metadata.json` (or `ro-crate-metadata.jsonld` in legacy crates for RO-Crate 1.0 or older) and `@type` `CreativeWork`. This descriptor MUST have an `about` property referencing the *Root Data Entity*'s `@id`.

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
```

```

        "about": {"@id": "./"},
        "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"}
    },

    {
        "@id": "./",
        "@type": "Dataset",
        ...
    }
]
}

```

Note: Even in Detached RO-Crate Packages, where the *RO-Crate Metadata File* may be absent or named with a prefix, the identifier `ro-crate-metadata.json` MUST be used within the *RO-Crate JSON-LD*.

The `conformsTo` of the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* SHOULD have a single value which is a versioned permalink URI of the RO-Crate specification that the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* conforms to. The URI SHOULD start with `https://w3id.org/ro/crate/`.

Note: In RO-Crates conforming to version 1.1 and earlier, `conformsTo` MAY be an array and can include RO-Crate profiles in addition to the base specification. In version 1.2 and later, it is now recommended that profile declarations are included on the *Root Data Entity* instead (see Direct Properties of the Root Data Entity).

6.1.1 Finding the Root Data Entity

Consumers processing the RO-Crate as a JSON-LD graph can find the *Root Data Entity* by following this algorithm:

1. For each entity in `@graph` array
2. .. if the `@id` is `ro-crate-metadata.json`
3. from this entity's `about` object, keep the `@id` URI as variable *root*
4. .. if the `@id` is `ro-crate-metadata.jsonld`
5. from this entity's `about` object, keep the `@id` URI as variable *legacyroot*
6. For each entity in `@graph` array
7. .. if the entity has an `@id` URI that matches a non-null *root* return it
8. For each entity in `@graph` array
9. .. if the entity has an `@id` URI that matches a non-null *legacyroot* return it
10. Fail with unknown root data entity.

Note that the above can be implemented efficiently by first building a map (`entity_map`) of all entities using their `@id` as keys (which is typically also helpful for further processing) and then performing a series of lookups. Ignoring the legacy case for now, this lookup code could be:

```

metadata_entity = entity_map["ro-crate-metadata.json"]
root_entity = entity_map[metadata_entity["about"]["@id"]]

```

See also the appendix on finding RO-Crate Root in RDF triple stores.

6.1.2 Purpose of Metadata Document

To ensure a base-line interoperability between RO-Crates, a minimum set of metadata is required for the *Root Data Entity*. As stated earlier the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is not an exhaustive manifest or inventory, that is, it does not necessarily list or describe all files in the package. For this reason, there are no minimum metadata requirements in terms of describing Data Entities (files and folders) other than the *Root Data Entity*. Extensions of RO-Crate dealing with specific types of dataset may apply further constraints or requirements of metadata beyond the Root Data Entity (see the appendix Extending RO-Crate).

The *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* MAY contain information such as licensing for the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* if metadata is licensed separately from the crate's Data entities.

The section below outlines the properties that the *Root Data Entity* MUST have.

6.2 Direct properties of the Root Data Entity

The *Root Data Entity* MUST have all of the properties listed below. Each property also has requirements that apply to its value:

- **@type**: MUST be Dataset or an array that contains Dataset
- **@id**: SHOULD be the string `./` or an absolute URI (see below)
- **name**: SHOULD identify the dataset to humans well enough to disambiguate it from other RO-Crates
- **description**: SHOULD further elaborate on the name to provide a summary of the context in which the dataset is important.
- **datePublished**: MUST be a single string value in ISO 8601 date format, SHOULD be specified to at least the precision of a day, and MAY be a timestamp down to the millisecond.
- **license**: SHOULD link to a *Contextual Entity* or *Data Entity* in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* with a name and description (see section on licensing). MAY, if necessary, be a textual description of how the RO-Crate may be used.

Note: These requirements are stricter than those published for Google Dataset Search which requires a Dataset to have a **name** and **description**.

Warning :The properties above are not sufficient to generate a DataCite citation. Advice on integrating with DataCite will be provided in a future version of this specification, or as an implementation guide.

Additional properties of *schema.org* types Dataset and CreativeWork MAY be added to further describe the RO-Crate as a whole, e.g. author, abstract, publisher. See sections contextual entities and provenance for further details.

If the RO-Crate conforms to one or more profiles, this should be described following the guidance in the section Declaring conformance of an RO-Crate profile.

6.2.1 Root Data Entity identifier

The *Root Data Entity*'s `@id` SHOULD be either `./` (indicating the directory of `ro-crate-metadata.json` is the RO-Crate Root), or an absolute URI.

Note: RO-Crates that have been assigned a *persistent identifier* (e.g. a DOI) MAY indicate this using identifier on the *Root Data Entity* using the approach set out in the Science On Schema.org guides, that is through a `PropertyValue` or MAY use a full persistent URL as the `@id` for the *Root Data Entity*.

Note: RO-Crate 1.1 and earlier recommended `identifier` to be plain string URIs. Clients SHOULD be permissive of an RO-Crate `identifier` being a string (which MAY be a URI), or a `@id` reference, which SHOULD be represented as a `PropertyValue` entity which MUST have a human readable `value`, and SHOULD have a `url` if the identifier is Web-resolvable. A citable representation of this persistent identifier MAY be given as a `description` of the `PropertyValue`, but as there are more than 10.000 known citation styles, no attempt should be made to parse this string.

6.2.1.1 Resolvable persistent identifiers and citation text It is RECOMMENDED that resolving the `identifier` programmatically returns the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* or an archive (e.g. ZIP) that contains the *RO-Crate Metadata File*, using content negotiation and/or Signposting. With an RO-Crate identifier that is persistent and resolvable in this way from a URI, the *Root Data Entity* SHOULD indicate this using the `cite-as` property according to RFC8574. Likewise, an HTTP/HTTPS server of the resolved RO-Crate Metadata Document or archive (possibly after redirection) SHOULD indicate that persistent identifier in its Signposting headers using `Link rel="cite-as"`.

Tip: The above `cite-as` MAY go to a repository landing page, and MAY require authentication, but MUST ultimately have the RO-Crate as a downloadable item, which SHOULD be programmatically accessible through content negotiation or Signposting (`Link rel="describedby"` for an *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, or `Link rel="item"` for an archive). To rather associate a textual scholarly citation for a crate (e.g. journal article), indicate instead a publication via `citation` property.

Any entity which is a subclass of `CreativeWork`, including Datasets like the *Root Data Entity*, MAY have a `creditText` property which provides a textual citation for the entity.

6.3 Minimal example of RO-Crate

The following *RO-Crate Metadata Document* represents a minimal description of an *RO-Crate* that also follows the identifier recommendations above for use in an *Attached RO-Crate Package*.

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
```

```

    "about": {"@id": "./"},
    "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"}
  },
  {
    "@id": "./",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "identifier": {"@id": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b"},
    "cite-as": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b",
    "datePublished": "2017",
    "name": "Data files associated with the manuscript:Effects of facilitated family case
    "description": "Palliative care planning for nursing home residents with advanced deme
    "license": {"@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/"},
    "creditText": "Agar, M. et al., 2017. Data supporting \"Effects of facilitated family
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/",
    "@type": "CreativeWork",
    "description": "This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommer
    "identifier": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/",
    "name": "Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 Australia (CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 AU)"
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b",
    "@type": "PropertyValue",
    "propertyID": "https://registry.identifiers.org/registry/doi",
    "value": "doi:10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b",
    "url": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b"
  }
]
}

```

Alternatively the following is also valid, this time using the DOI as the @id of the *Root Data Entity*:

```

{
  "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "about": {"@id": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b"},
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"}
},
{
  "@id": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "cite-as": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b",
  "datePublished": "2017",
  "name": "Data files associated with the manuscript:Effects of facilitated family case
  "description": "Palliative care planning for nursing home residents with advanced deme
  "license": {"@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/au/"},
  "creditText": "Agar, M. et al., 2017. Data supporting \"Effects of facilitated family
}

```

7 Data Entities

The primary purpose for RO-Crate is to gather and describe a set of *Data Entities* in the form of:

- Actual files which are datastreams available on the local file system or over the web – when represented in the RO-Crate Metadata Document, these have the type **File**.
- Folders (or directories) of files – represented using the type **Dataset**.

An entity which has **File** or **Dataset** as one of its **@type** values:

- Is considered to be a *Data Entity* if its **@id** is an absolute URI or a relative URI.
- MAY have an **@id** which is a local identifier beginning with a **#**, in which case it is **not** considered to be a **Data Entity**.

The requirements for **File** and **Dataset** are set out below.

The Data Entities can be further described by referencing contextual entities such as persons, organizations and publications.

7.1 Referencing files and folders from the Root Data Entity

Where files and folders are represented as *Data Entities* in the RO-Crate JSON-LD, these MUST be linked to, either directly or indirectly, from the Root Data Entity using the **hasPart** property. Directory hierarchies MAY be represented with nested **Dataset Data Entities**, or the Root Data Entity MAY refer to files anywhere in the hierarchy using **hasPart**.

Data Entities representing files MUST have **"File"** as a value for **@type**. **File** is an RO-Crate alias for <http://schema.org/MediaObject>. The term *File* includes:

- Resources which are available locally (applicable only in the context of *Attached RO-Crate Packages*) and
- Web-based Data Entities which can be downloaded and saved as a file.

The rules for the **@id** property of Files are set out below.

In all cases, **@type** MAY be an array to also specify a more specific type, e.g. **"@type": ["File", "ComputationalWorkflow"]**

There is no requirement to represent *every* file and folder in an RO-Crate as *Data Entities* in the *RO-Crate JSON-LD*. Reasons for not describing files would include that the files: - are described in some other way, for example a manifest or another package management system, - are supporting files for a software application, - have metadata embedded in their filenames or paths which can be documented without having to describe every file, - have a purpose that is unknown to the crate author, but they need to be preserved as part of an archive.

In any of the above cases where files are not described, a directory containing a set of files MAY be described using a **Dataset Data Entity** that encapsulates

the files with a `description` property that explains the contents. If the RO-Crate file structure is flat, or files are not grouped together, a `description` property on the *Root Data Entity* may be used, or a `Dataset` with a local reference beginning with `#` (e.g. to describe a certain type of file which occurs throughout the crate). This approach is recommended for RO-Crates which are to be deposited in a long-term archive.

7.2 Encoding file paths in @ids

Note that all `@id` identifiers must be valid URI references. Care must be taken to express any relative paths using `/` separator, correct casing, and escape special characters like space (`%20`) and percent (`%25`), for instance a *File Data Entity* from the Windows path `Results and Diagrams\almost-50%.png` becomes `"@id": "Results%20and%20Diagrams/almost-50%25.png"` in the *RO-Crate JSON-LD*.

In this document the term *URI* includes international *IRIs*; the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* is always UTF-8 and international characters in identifiers SHOULD be written using native UTF-8 characters (*IRIs*), however traditional URL encoding of Unicode characters with `%` MAY appear in `@id` strings. Example: `"@id": ".mp4"` is preferred over the equivalent `"@id": "%E9%9D%A2%E8%AF%95.mp4"`

7.3 Example Attached RO-Crate Package

The following is an example of an *Attached RO-Crate Package* linking to a file and folders.

The file layout of the example is:

```
<RO-Crate root>/
|  ro-crate-metadata.json
|  cp7glop.ai
|  lots_of_little_files/
|    | file1
|    | file2
|    | ...
|    | file54
```

An example *RO-Crate JSON-LD* for the above would be as follows.

This example contains both a File Data Entity and a Directory Data Entity.

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "./"}
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
```

```

    "@type": [
      "Dataset"
    ],
    "name": "Example Dataset",
    "datePublished": "2016-02-01",
    "author": "https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4953-0830",
    "license": "CC-BY",
    "hasPart": [
      {
        "@id": "cp7glop.ai"
      },
      {
        "@id": "lots_of_little_files/"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "@id": "cp7glop.ai",
    "@type": "File",
    "name": "Diagram showing trend to increase",
    "contentSize": "383766",
    "description": "Illustrator file for Glop Pot",
    "encodingFormat": "application/pdf"
  },
  {
    "@id": "lots_of_little_files/",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "name": "Too many files",
    "description": "This directory contains many small files -- the name of the file is
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4953-0830",
    "@type": "Person",
    "name": "Michael Lake",
  }
]
}

```

7.4 Core Metadata for Data Entities

7.4.1 File Data Entity

A File *Data Entity* MUST have the following properties:

- `@type`: MUST be `File`, or an array where `File` is one of the values.
- `@id`: MUST be a relative or absolute URI.

Further constraints on the `@id` are dependent on whether the File entity is being considered as part of an *Attached RO-Crate Package* or *Detached RO-Crate Package*.

1. For an *Attached RO-Crate Package*:

- `@id` MUST be one of either: a. A relative URI, indicating that a file MUST be present at the path `@id` relative to the *RO-Crate Root*. b. An absolute URI, indicating that the entity is a Web-based Data Entity.

A File in an *Attached RO-Crate Package* MAY have also a `contentURL` property which corresponds to a download link for the file. Following the link (allowing for HTTP redirects) SHOULD directly download the file.

2. For a *Detached RO-Crate Package* `@id` MUST be an Absolute URI; all File Data Entities are Web-based Data Entities.

Additionally, File entities SHOULD have:

- name giving a human readable name (not necessarily the filename)
- description giving a longer description, e.g. the role of this file within this crate
- `encodingFormat` indicating the the IANA media type as a string (e.g. “text/plain”) and/or a reference to file format contextual entity.
- `conformsTo` to a contextual entity of type Profile, that indicate a profile of the encoding format, if applicable
- `contentSize` with the size of the file in bytes

RO-Crate’s File is an alias for schema.org type MediaObject, any of its properties MAY also be used (adding contextual entities as needed). Files on the web SHOULD also use `identifier`, `url`, `subjectOf`, and/or `mainEntityOfPage`.

A File entity MAY have an `@id` that is a local identifier beginning with #, in which case it is **not** considered to be a Data Entity, though it MAY still be linked to the *Root Data Entity* via `hasPart`. This is useful for describing physical files which are deliberately not present, for example if they are expected to be created by running a process. In this case, the `localPath` property SHOULD be used to indicate that a File could be found at that path in some circumstances.

Note: It is up to implementers to decide whether to offer some form of URL “link checker” service for Web-based Data Entities for both attached and detached RO-Crate Packages. If `contentUrl` has more than one value, then a checker service SHOULD try each provided value until one resolves and returns a correct `contentSize`.

7.4.2 Directory Data Entity

A Dataset (directory) *Data Entity* MUST have the following properties:

- `@type` MUST be `Dataset` or an array where `Dataset` is one of the values.
- `@id` MUST be either:
 - In an *Attached RO-Crate Package* ONLY – a *URI Path* that SHOULD end with /. This MUST resolve to a directory which is present in the RO-Crate Root along with its parent directories.
 - An absolute URI which SHOULD resolve to a programmatic listing of the content of the “directory” (e.g. another RO-Crate).

For a *Detached RO-Crate Package*: * The `localPath` property MAY be used to indicate the directory path to use when converting from a *Detached* to an *Attached RO-Crate Package*.

Additionally, `Dataset` entities SHOULD have:

- name giving a human readable name (not necessarily the directory name)
- description giving a longer description, e.g. the content of this directory
- `hasPart` listing directly contained Data Entities

Any of the properties of schema.org `Dataset` MAY additionally be used (adding contextual entities as needed). Directories on the web SHOULD also provide `distribution`.

A `Dataset` which has an `@id` that is a local identifier beginning with `#` is **not** considered a Data Entity – but MAY be used to describe a set of files or other resources, and MAY still be linked to the *Root Data Entity* via `hasPart`. For example, if the dataset contained a large number of `*.ai` files which were spread throughout the crate structure and which did not have corresponding File Data Entities, then a approach to describing these files would be:

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": [
    "Dataset"
  ],
  "hasPart": [
    {
      "@id": "#ai-files"
    }
  ],
},
{
  "@id": "#ai-files",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": ".ai Files",
  "description": "This dataset contains some files with the extension '.ai' which despit
}
```

7.4.3 Web-based Data Entities

Using Web-based Data Entities can be important particularly where a file can't be included in the *RO-Crate Root* because of licensing concerns, large data sizes, privacy, or where it is desirable to link to the latest online version.

Example of an RO-Crate including a *File Data Entity* external to the *RO-Crate Root* (file entity <https://zenodo.org/record/3541888/files/ro-crate-1.0.0.pdf>):

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "."}
    }
  ],
}
```

```

    "@id": "./",
    "@type": [
      "Dataset"
    ],
    "hasPart": [
      {
        "@id": "survey-responses-2019.csv"
      },
      {
        "@id": "https://zenodo.org/record/3541888/files/ro-crate-1.0.0.pdf"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "@id": "survey-responses-2019.csv",
    "@type": "File",
    "name": "Survey responses",
    "contentSize": "26452",
    "encodingFormat": "text/csv"
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://zenodo.org/record/3541888/files/ro-crate-1.0.0.pdf",
    "@type": "File",
    "name": "R0-Crate specification",
    "contentSize": "310691",
    "description": "R0-Crate specification",
    "encodingFormat": "application/pdf"
  }
]
}

```

Additional care SHOULD be taken to improve persistence and long-term preservation of web resources included in an RO-Crate, as they can be more difficult to archive or move along with the *RO-Crate Root*, and may change intentionally or unintentionally, leaving the RO-Crate with incomplete or outdated information.

File Data Entities with an @id URI outside the *RO-Crate Root* SHOULD at the time of RO-Crate creation be directly downloadable by a simple non-interactive retrieval (e.g. HTTP GET) of a single data stream, permitting redirections and HTTP/HTTPS authentication. For instance, in the example above, <https://zenodo.org/record/3541888> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3541888> cannot be used as @id as retrieving these URLs gives a HTML landing page rather than the desired PDF as indicated by encodingFormat.

Note: *Web-based Data Entities* SHOULD NOT reference intermediate resources such as splash-pages, search services or web-based viewer applications.

As files on the web may change, the timestamp property sdDatePublished SHOULD be included to indicate when the absolute URL was accessed, and derived metadata like encodingFormat and contentSize were considered to be representative:

```

{
  "@id": "https://zenodo.org/record/3541888/files/ro-crate-1.0.0.pdf",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "RO-Crate specification",
  "contentSize": "310691",
  "encodingFormat": "application/pdf",
  "sdDatePublished": "2020-04-09T13:09:21+01:00Z"
}

```

Web-based entities MAY use the property `localPath` to indicate a path that can be used to when downloading the data in an *Attached RO-Crate Package* context. This may be used to instantiate local copies of web-based resources in an *Attached RO-Crate Package* or as part of a process to download local resources from a *Detached RO-Crate Package* relative to a new root directory.

```

{
  "@id": "https://zenodo.org/record/3541888/files/ro-crate-1.0.0.pdf",
  "localPath": "docs/ro-crate-1.0.0.pdf",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "RO-Crate specification",
  "contentSize": "310691",
  "encodingFormat": "application/pdf",
  "sdDatePublished": "2020-04-09T13:09:21+01:00Z"
}

```

Note: Do not use web-based URI identifiers for files which *are* present in the crate root, see below.

7.4.4 Data entities in an *Attached RO-Crate* that are also on the web

File Data Entities that are present as local files may already have a corresponding web presence, for instance a landing page that describes the file, including persistent identifiers (e.g. DOI) resolving to an intermediate HTML page instead of the downloadable file directly.

These MAY be included for File Data Entities as additional metadata, regardless of whether the File is included in the *RO-Crate Root* directory or exists on the Web, by using the properties:

- identifier for formal identifier strings such as DOIs
- `contentUrl` with a string URL corresponding to a *download* link. Following the link (allowing for HTTP redirects) SHOULD directly download the file.
- `url` with a string URL for a download/landing page for this particular file (e.g. direct download is not available)
- `subjectOf` to a CreativeWork (or WebPage) that mentions this file or its content (but also other resources)
- `mainEntityOfPage` to a CreativeWork (or WebPage) that primarily describes this file (or its content)

Note that if a local file is intended to be packaged within an *Attached RO-Crate Package*, the `@id` property MUST be a *URI Path* relative to the *RO Crate Root*,

for example `survey-responses-2019.csv` as in the example below, where the `contentUrl` points to a download endpoint as a string.

```
{
  "@id": "survey-responses-2019.csv",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Survey responses",
  "encodingFormat": "text/csv",
  "contentUrl": "http://example.com/downloads/2019/survey-responses-2019.csv",
  "subjectOf": {"@id": "http://example.com/reports/2019/annual-survey.html"}
},
{
  "@id": "http://example.com/reports/2019/annual-survey.html",
  "@type": "WebPage",
  "name": "Survey responses (landing page)"
}
```

7.4.5 Directories on the web; dataset distributions

A *Directory File Entity* or Dataset identifier expressed as an absolute URL on the web can be harder to download than a File because it consists of multiple resources. It is RECOMMENDED that such directories have a complete listing of their content in `hasPart`, enabling download traversal, or are themselves RO-Crates (see Referencing other RO-Crates).

7.4.5.1 Downloadable dataset Alternatively, a common mechanism to provide downloads of a reasonably sized directory is as an archive file in formats such as `application/zip` or `application/gzip`, described as a `DataDownload`.

```
{
  "@id": "lots_of_little_files/",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "Too many files",
  "description": "This directory contains many small files, that we're not going to desc",
  "distribution": {"@id": "http://example.com/downloads/2020/lots_of_little_files.zip"}
},
{
  "@id": "http://example.com/downloads/2020/lots_of_little_files.zip",
  "@type": "DataDownload",
  "encodingFormat": ["application/zip", {"@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRO"},
  "contentSize": "82818928"
}
```

Similarly, the *RO-Crate Root* entity (or a reference to another RO-Crate as a `Dataset`) may provide a distribution URL, in which case the download SHOULD be an archive that contains the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* (either directly in the archive's root, or within a single folder in the archive), indicated by a version-less `conformsTo`:

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
```

```

    "identifier": {"@id": "https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.775.1"},
    "cite-as": "https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.775.1",
    "name": "Research Object Crate for Jupyter Notebook Molecular Structure Checking",
    "distribution": {"@id": "https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/775/ro_crate?version=1"},
    "...": ""
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/775/ro_crate?version=1",
    "@type": "DataDownload",
    "encodingFormat": ["application/zip", {"@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRO"},
    "conformsTo": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate" }
  }
}

```

In all cases, consumers should be aware that a `DataDownload` is a snapshot that may not reflect the current state of the `Dataset` or RO-Crate.

7.5 Adding detailed descriptions of File encodings

The above example provides a media type for the file `cp7glop.ai` – which is useful as it may not be apparent that the file is readable as a PDF file from the extension alone. To add more detail, encodings SHOULD be linked using a PRONOM identifier to a *Contextual Entity* with `@type` array containing `WebPage` and `Standard`.

```

  {
    "@id": "cp7glop.ai",
    "@type": "File",
    "name": "Glop Plot map",
    "contentSize": "383766",
    "description": "Illustrator file for Glop Pot",
    "encodingFormat": ["application/pdf", {"@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRO"},
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/19",
    "name": "Acrobat PDF 1.5 -- Portable Document Format",
    "@type": ["WebPage", "Standard"]
  }
}

```

If there is no PRONOM identifier (and typically no media type string), then a contextual entity with a different URL as an `@id` MAY be used, e.g. documentation page of a software's file format. The contextual entity SHOULD NOT include `Standard` in its `@type` if the page does not sufficiently document the format. The `@type` SHOULD include `WebPage`, or MAY include `WebPageElement` to indicate a section of the page.

For example, `.trr` is an internal GROMACS file format that is not further documented as a standard, but is referenced from a `WebPageElement` addressable by an `#anchor`:

```

  {
    "@id": "traj.trr",
    "@type": "File",
  }

```

```

    "name": "Trajectory",
    "description": "Trajectory of molecular dynamics simulation using GROMACS",
    "contentSize": "45512",
    "encodingFormat": {"@id": "https://manual.gromacs.org/documentation/2021/reference-man
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://manual.gromacs.org/documentation/2021/reference-manual/file-formats.ht
    "@type": "WebPageElement",
    "name": "GROMACS trajectory of a simulation (trr)"
  }
}

```

If there is no web-accessible description for a file format it SHOULD be described locally in the RO-Crate, for example in a Markdown file:

```

{
  "@id": "some-file.some_extension",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Some file",
  "description": "A file in a non-standard format",
  "contentSize": "120",
  "encodingFormat": ["text/plain", {"@id": "some_extension.md"}]
},
{
  "@id": "some_extension.md",
  "@type": ["File", "CreativeWork"],
  "name": "Description of some_extension text-based file format",
  "encodingFormat": "text/markdown"
}

```

7.6 File format profiles

Some generic file formats like `application/json` may be specialized using a *profile* document that defines expectations for the file's content as expected by some applications, by using `conformsTo` to a contextual entity with types `CreativeWork` and `Profile`:

```

{
  "@id": "attributes.csv",
  "@type": "File",
  "encodingFormat": ["text/csv", {"@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/x-fmt
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://docs.ropensci.org/dataspice/#create-spice"}
},
{
  "@id": "https://docs.ropensci.org/dataspice/#create-spice",
  "@type": ["CreativeWork", "Profile"],
  "name": "dataspice CSV profile"
}

```

Tip: Profiles expressed in formal languages (e.g. XML Schema for validation) can have their own `encodingFormat` and `conformsTo` to indicate their file format.

Note: The Metadata Descriptor `ro-crate-metadata.json` is not a data entity, but is described with `conformsTo` to an *implicit contextual entity* for the RO-Crate specification, a profile of JSON-LD. RO-Crates themselves can be specialized using Profile Crates, specified with `conformsTo` on the Root Data Entity.

7.7 Referencing other RO-Crates

A referenced RO-Crate is also a Dataset Data Entity, but where its `hasPart` does not need to be listed. Instead, its content and further metadata is available from its own RO-Crate Metadata Document, which may be retrieved or packaged within an archive. An entity representing a referenced RO-Crate SHOULD have `conformsTo` pointing to the generic RO-Crate profile using the fixed URI `https://w3id.org/ro/crate`.

This section defines how a *referencing* RO-Crate (“A”) can declare Data Entities within A’s RO-Crate Metadata Document, in order to indicate a *referenced* RO-Crate (“B”). There are different options on how to find the identifier to assign to B in A, and how a consumer of A finding such a reference can find the corresponding RO-Crate Metadata Document for B.

7.7.1 Referencing RO-Crates that have a persistent identifier

If the referenced RO-Crate B has an `identifier` declared as B’s Root Data Entity identifier, then this is a *persistent identifier* which SHOULD be used as the URI in the `@id` of the corresponding entity in RO-Crate A. For instance, if RO-Crate B had declared the identifier `https://pid.example.com/another-crate/` then RO-Crate A can reference B as an entity:

```
{
  "@id": "https://pid.example.com/another-crate/",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "conformsTo": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate" }
}
```

Tip: The `conformsTo` generic RO-Crate profile on the `Dataset` entity that represents B MUST be version-less. The referenced RO-Crate B is **not** required to conform to the same version of the RO-Crate specification as A’s RO-Crate Metadata Document.

Warning :It is NOT RECOMMENDED to declare the generic profile `https://w3id.org/ro/crate` on the referencing RO-Crate A’s own Root Data Entity, see metadata descriptor.

Consumers that find a reference to a `Dataset` with the generic RO-Crate profile indicated MAY attempt to resolve the persistent identifier, but SHOULD NOT assume that the `@id` directly resolves to an RO-Crate Metadata Document. See section Retrieving an RO-Crate below for the recommended algorithm.

If an `identifier` is not declared in a referenced RO-Crate B, follow the steps in Determining entity identifier for a referenced RO-Crate instead.

7.7.2 Determining entity identifier for a referenced RO-Crate

In some cases, if the referenced RO-Crate B has not got a resolvable `identifier` declared, additional steps are needed to find the correct `@id` to use:

1. If RO-Crate A is an Attached RO-Crate Package and RO-Crate B is a nested folder within A (e.g. `another-crate/`), then B SHOULD be treated as an *Attached RO-Crate Package* (e.g. it has `another-crate/ro-crate-metadata.json`) and the relative path (`another-crate/`) SHOULD be used directly as `@id` of a Directory Data Entity within RO-Crate A.
2. If B's *Root Data Entity* has an `@id` that is an absolute URI, and that URI resolves according to Retrieving an RO-Crate, then that can be used as the `@id` of the `Dataset` entity in A, equivalent to the `identifier` case above.
 1. If the absolute URI has Signposting declared for a `Link:` with `rel=cite-as`, then that link MAY be considered as an equivalent permalink for B and no further properties are needed.
 2. Otherwise, as the URI was not declared as a persistent identifier, the timestamp property `sdDatePublished` SHOULD be included to indicate when the absolute URI was accessed.
3. If B's *RO-Crate Metadata Document* was located on the Web, but uses a relative URI reference for its Root Data Entity (`./`), then its absolute URI can be determined from the RFC 3986 algorithm for establishing a base URI. For example, if root `{"@id": " ./" }` is in metadata document `http://example.com/another-crate/ro-crate-metadata.json`, then the absolute URI for the `Dataset` entity is `http://example.com/another-crate/` (with the trailing `/`). If that URI is resolvable as in point 2, it can be used as equivalent `@id` (with `sdDatePublished` declared if necessary). It is NOT RECOMMENDED to resolve a relative root identifier if the metadata document was retrieved from a URI that does not end with `/ro-crate-metadata.json`, `/*-ro-crate-metadata.json` or `/ro-crate-metadata.jsonld` – these are not part of a valid Attached or Detached RO-Crate Package.
4. If RO-Crate B is not on the Web, and does not have a persistent identifier, e.g. is within a ZIP file or local file system, then a non-resolvable identifier could be established. See appendix Establishing a base URI inside a ZIP file, e.g. `arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/` if using a randomly generated UUID. This method may also be used if the above steps fail for an RO-Crate Metadata Document that is on the Web. In this case, the referenced RO-Crate entity MUST either declare a referenced metadata document or distribution.

7.7.3 Referencing another metadata document

If a referenced RO-Crate Metadata Document is known at a given URI or path, but its corresponding RO-Crate identifier can't be determined as above (e.g. Retrieving an RO-Crate fails or requires heuristics), then a referenced metadata descriptor entity SHOULD be added. For instance, if `http://example.com/another-crate/ro-crate-metadata.json` resolves to an RO-Crate Metadata Document describing root `./`, but

`http://example.com/another-crate/` always returns a HTML page without Signposting to the metadata document, then `subjectOf` SHOULD be added to an explicit metadata descriptor entity, which has `encodingFormat` declared for JSON-LD:

```
{
  "@id": "http://example.com/another-crate/",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "conformsTo": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate" },
  "subjectOf": { "@id": "http://example.com/another-crate/ro-crate-metadata.json" }
},
{
  "@id": "http://example.com/another-crate/ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "encodingFormat": "application/ld+json",
  "sdDatePublished": "2024-08-22T23:57:03+01:00"
}
```

Tip: Counter to file format profile recommendations, the referenced RO-Crate metadata descriptor SHOULD NOT include its own `conformsTo` declarations to `https://w3id.org/ro/crate` or reference the dataset with `about`; this is to avoid confusion with the referencing RO-Crate's own metadata descriptor.

7.7.4 Profiles of referenced crates

If the referenced crate conforms to a given RO-Crate profile, this MAY be indicated by expanding `conformsTo` on the Dataset to an array to reference the profile as a contextual entity:

```
{
  "@id": "https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.26.1",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "conformsTo": [
    { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate" },
    { "@id": "https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0" }
  ]
},
{ "@id": "https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0",
  "@type": ["CreativeWork", "Profile"],
  "name": "Workflow RO-Crate Profile",
  "version": "1.0"
}
```

Note: The profile declaration of a referenced crate is a hint. Consumers should check `conformsTo` as declared in the retrieved RO-Crate, as it may have been updated after this RO-Crate.

7.7.5 Retrieving an RO-Crate

To resolve a reference to an RO-Crate, but where `subjectOf` or `distribution` is unknown (e.g. an RO-Crate is cited from a journal article), the below approach is recommended to retrieve its RO-Crate Metadata Document:

1. Assuming the URI is a permalink, after following HTTP redirects without content negotiation, try Signposting to look for Link headers that reference `Link rel="describedby"` for an *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, or `Link rel="item"` for a distribution archive – in either case prefer a link with `profile="https://w3id.org/ro/crate"` declared. For example, signposting for `https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.120.5` leads to the archive `https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/120/ro_crate?version=5` as:

```
curl --location --head https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.120.5
```

```
HTTP/2 302
```

```
Location: https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/120?version=5
```

```
HTTP/2 200
```

```
Content-Type: text/html; charset=UTF-8
```

```
Link: <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/120/ro_crate?version=5> ;  
      rel="item" ; type="application/zip" ;  
      profile="https://w3id.org/ro/crate"
```

2. HTTP Content-negotiation for the RO-Crate media type, for example:

Requesting `https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0`

with HTTP header `Accept: application/ld+json;profile=https://w3id.org/ro/crate`

redirects to the *RO-Crate Metadata file* `https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-cr`

3. The above approaches may fail or return a HTML page, e.g. for content-delivery networks that do not support content-negotiation.

4. An optional heuristic fallback is to try resolving the path `./ro-crate-metadata.json` from the *resolved* URI (after permalink redirects). For example:

If permalink `https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0`

redirects to `https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/index.html`

(a HTML page), then try retrieving `https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-cr`

5. If the retrieved resource is a ZIP file (`Content-Type: application/zip`), then extract `ro-crate-metadata.json`, or, if the archive root only contains a single folder (e.g. `folder1/`), extract `folder1/ro-crate-metadata.json`
6. If the retrieved resource is a BagIt archive, e.g. containing a single folder `folder1` with `folder1/bagit.txt`, then extract and verify BagIt checksums before returning the bag's `data/ro-crate-metadata.json`
7. If the returned/extracted document is valid JSON-LD and has a Root Data Entity, this is the RO-Crate Metadata File.

Tip: Some PID providers such as DataCite may respond to content-negotiation and provide their own JSON-LD, which do not describe an RO-Crate (the `profile=` was ignored). The use of Signposting allows the repository to explicitly provide the RO-Crate.

8 Representing Contextual Entities

The RO-Crate SHOULD contain additional information about *Contextual Entities* for the use of both humans (in `ro-crate-preview.html`) and machines (in `ro-crate-metadata.json`). This also helps to maximize the extent to which an *RO-Crate* is self-contained and self-describing, in that it reduces the need for the consumer of an RO-Crate to refer to external information which may change or become unavailable over time.

8.1 Contextual vs Data entities

RO-Crate distinguishes between *contextual entities* and *data entities*.

Data entities primarily exist in their own right as a file or directory (which may be in the *RO-Crate Root* directory or downloadable by URL).

Contextual entities however primarily exist outside the digital sphere (e.g. People, Places) or are conceptual descriptions that primarily exist as metadata, like GeoCoordinates and ContactPoint.

Some contextual entities can also be considered data entities – for instance the license property refers to a CreativeWork that can reasonably be downloaded, however a license document is not usually considered as part of research outputs and would therefore typically not be included in `hasPart` on the root data entity.

Likewise, some data entities may also be described as contextual entities, for instance a `File` that is also a `ScholarlyArticle`. In such cases the *contextual data entity* MUST be described as a single JSON-LD object in the RO-Crate Metadata JSON-LD `@graph` and SHOULD list both relevant data and contextual types in a `@type` array.

Tip: Files in the *RO-Crate Root* are not necessarily data entities – the RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor is a file in the *RO-Crate Root*, but is considered a *Contextual Entity* as it is describing the RO-Crate, rather than being part of it. On the other hand, the Root Data Entity is a data entity within its own metadata file.

The RO-Crate Metadata JSON-LD `@graph` MUST NOT list multiple entities with the same `@id`; behaviour of consumers of an RO-Crate encountering multiple entities with the same `@id` is undefined.

8.2 Identifiers for contextual entities

A challenge can be how to assign identifiers for contextual entities, that is deciding on their `@id` value.

If an existing permalink (e.g. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097>) or other absolute URI (e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Josiah_S._Carberry) is reasonably unique for that entity, that URI SHOULD be used as identifier for the contextual entity in preference of an identifier local to the RO-Crate (e.g. `#josiah` or `#0fa587c6-4580-4ece-a5df-69af3c5590e3`).

Care should be taken to not describe two conceptually different contextual entities with the same identifier - e.g. if https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Josiah_S._Carberry

is a Person it SHOULD NOT also be a CreativeWork (although this example is a fictional person!).

Where a related URL exists that may not be unique enough to serve as identifier, it can instead be added to a contextual entity using the property url.

See the appendix on JSON-LD identifiers for details.

8.3 People

A core principle of Linked Data is to use URIs to identify important entities such as people. The following is the minimum recommended way of representing an author of an RO-Crate. The author property MAY also be applied to a directory (Dataset), a File or other CreativeWork entities.

```
{
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "@id": "./",
  "...": "...",
  "author": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8367-6908"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8367-6908",
  "@type": "Person",
  "affiliation": "University of Technology Sydney",
  "name": "J. Xuan"
}
```

This uses an ORCID to unambiguously identify an author, represented as a *Contextual Entity* of type Person.

Note the string *value* for the organizational affiliation. This SHOULD be improved by also providing a *Contextual Entity* for the organization (see example below).

8.4 Organizations as values

An Organization SHOULD be the value for the publisher property of a Dataset or ScholarlyArticle.

```
{
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "@id": "./",
  "...": "...",
  "publisher": {
    "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041",
  "@type": "Organization",
}
```

```

    "name": "University of Technology Sydney",
    "url": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041"
  }

```

An Organization SHOULD also be used for a Person's affiliation property.

```

{
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "@id": "./",
  "...": "...",
  "publisher": {
    "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041"
  },
  "author": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3545-944X"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "name": "University of Technology Sydney"
},
{
  "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3545-944X",
  "@type": "Person",
  "affiliation": {
    "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041"
  },
  "email": "peter.sefton@uts.edu.au",
  "name": "Peter Sefton"
}

```

8.5 Contact information

An RO-Crate SHOULD have contact information, using a contextual entity of type ContactPoint. Note that in Schema.org Dataset does not currently have the corresponding contactPoint property, so the contact point would need to be given through a Person or Organization contextual entity which are related to the Dataset via a author or publisher property.

```

{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "...": "...",
  "author": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6121-5409"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6121-5409",
  "@type": "Person",

```

```

    "contactPoint": {
      "@id": "mailto:tim.luckett@uts.edu.au"
    },
    "familyName": "Luckett",
    "givenName": "Tim",
    "identifier": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6121-5409",
    "name": "Tim Luckett"
  },
  {
    "@id": "mailto:tim.luckett@uts.edu.au",
    "@type": "ContactPoint",
    "contactType": "customer service",
    "email": "tim.luckett@uts.edu.au",
    "identifier": "tim.luckett@uts.edu.au",
    "url": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6121-5409"
  }
}

```

8.6 Publications via citation property

To associate a publication with a dataset the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* MUST include a URL (for example a DOI URL) as the `@id` of a publication using the citation property.

For example:

```

{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "...": "...",
  "citation": {
    "@id": "https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2014.2386282"
  }
}

```

The publication SHOULD be described further as an additional contextual entity of type `ScholarlyArticle` or `CreativeWork`.

```

{
  "@id": "https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2014.2386282",
  "@type": "ScholarlyArticle",
  "author": [
    {
      "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8367-6908"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0690-4732"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3960-0583"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6953-3986"
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    }
  ],
  "identifier": "https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2014.2386282",
  "issn": "2168-2267",
  "name": "Topic Model for Graph Mining",
  "journal": "IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics",
  "datePublished": "2015",
  "creditText": "J. Xuan, J. Lu, G. Zhang and X. Luo, \"Topic Model for Graph Mining,\" in
}

```

citation MAY also be used with other data and contextual entities:

```

{
  "@id": "communities-2018.csv",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Snapshot of RO Community efforts",
  "citation": {
    "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1313066"
  },
  "encodingFormat": "text/csv"
}

```

A data entity MAY provide a published DOI identifier that primarily captures that file or dataset. A citation MAY also be provided:

```

{
  "@id": "figure.png",
  "@type": ["File", "ImageObject"],
  "name": "XXL-CT-scan of an XXL Tyrannosaurus rex skull",
  "identifier": {
    "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3479743"
  },
  "citation": {
    "@id": "http://ndt.net/?id=19249"
  },
  "encodingFormat": "image/png"
},
{
  "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3479743",
  "@type": "PropertyValue",
  "propertyID": "https://registry.identifiers.org/registry/doi",
  "value": "doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3479743",
  "url": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3479743"
},
{
  "@id": "http://ndt.net/?id=19249",
  "@type": "ScholarlyArticle",
  "url": "http://ndt.net/?id=19249",
  "name": "An XXL-CT-scan of an XXL Tyrannosaurus rex skull. 19th World Conference on Non-
  "creditText": "Reims, N., Schulp, A., Böhnel, M., & Larson, P. (2016). An XXL-CT-scan of
}

```

8.7 Publisher

The Root Data Entity SHOULD have a publisher property. This SHOULD be an Organization though it MAY be a Person.

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "...": "...",
  "publisher": {
    "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "identifier": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041",
  "name": "University of Technology Sydney"
}
```

8.8 Funding and grants

To associate a research project with a Dataset, the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* SHOULD contain an entity for the project using type Organization, referenced by a funder property. The project Organization SHOULD in turn reference any external funder, either by using its URL as an @id or via a *Contextual Entity* describing the funder.

Tip: To make it very clear where funding is coming from, the *Root Data Entity* SHOULD also reference funders directly, as well as via a chain of references.

```
{
  "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009240",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "funder": {
    "@id": "https://ror.org/038sjwq14"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "https://ereseach.uts.edu.au/projects/provisioner",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "description": "The University of Technology Sydney Provisioner project is ...",
  "funder": [
    {
      "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://ands.org.au"
    }
  ],
  "identifier": "https://ereseach.uts.edu.au/projects/provisioner",
  "name": "Provisioner"
}
```

```

},
{
  "@id": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "identifier": "https://ror.org/03f0f6041",
  "name": "University of Technology Sydney"
},
{
  "@id": "https://ands.org.au",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "description": "The core purpose of the Australian National Data Service (ANDS) is ...",
  "identifier": "https://ands.org.au",
  "name": "Australian National Data Service"
}

```

8.9 Licensing, Access control and copyright

If a Data Entity has a license that is different from the license on the *Root Data Entity*, the entity SHOULD have a license property referencing a *Contextual Entity* with a type `CreativeWork` to describe the license. The `@id` of the license SHOULD be its URL (e.g. a Creative Commons License URL) and, when possible, a summary of the license included using the description property.

The below *Data Entity* has a `copyrightHolder` which is different from its author. There is a reference to an Organization describing the copyright holder and, to give credit, a `sameAs` relation to a web page. The license property here refers to <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> which is expanded in a separate contextual entity.

```

{
  "@id": "SciDataCon Presentations/AAA_Pilot_Project_Abstract.html",
  "@type": "File",
  "contentSize": "17085",
  "copyrightHolder": {
    "@id": "https://www.idrc.ca/"
  },
  "author": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0068-716X"
  },
  "description": "Abstract for the Pilot Project initial findings",
  "encodingFormat": "text/html",
  "license": {
    "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"
  },
  "sameAs": "https://www.scidatacon.org/2016/sessions/56/paper/265/"
},
{
  "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "name": "CC BY 4.0",
  "description": "Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License"
}

```

```

},
{
  "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0068-716X",
  "@type": "Person",
  "identifier": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0068-716X",
  "name": "Cameron Neylon"
},
{
  "@id": "https://www.idrc.ca/",
  "@type": "Organization",
  "description": "Canadian Frown Corporation and funder of development research",
  "identifier": "IDRC",
  "name": "International Development Research Center"
}
}

```

8.9.1 Metadata license

In some cases the license of the RO-Crate metadata (the JSON-LD statements in the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor*) is different from the license on the Root Data Entity and its content (*data entities* indicated by `hasPart`).

For instance, a common pattern for repositories is to license metadata as CC0 Public Domain Dedication, while data is licensed as CC-BY or similar. This pattern allows metadata to be combined freely (e.g. the DataCite knowledge graph), while redistribution of data files would require explicit attribution and statement of their license.

To express that the metadata license is different from the one of the *Root Data Entity*, expand the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* to include `license`:

```

{
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "identifier": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "about": {
    "@id": "./"
  },
  "license": {
    "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "...": "...",
  "license": {
    "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"
  }
}
}

```

If no explicit `license` is expressed on the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor*, the `license` expressed on the *Root Data Entity* applies also to the RO-Crate meta-

data.

8.10 Extra metadata such as Exif

Schema.org has a generic extension mechanism for encoding arbitrary properties and values which are not available as Schema.org properties. An example of this is the Schema.org recommended way (see example 2) of including Exif technical image metadata.

To include EXIF, or other data which can be encoded as property/value pairs, add an array of references to *Anonymous Entities* which encode each property. This example shows one property of several hundred.

```
{
  "@id": "pics/2017-06-11%2012.56.14.jpg",
  "@type": ["File", "ImageObject"],
  "contentSize": "5114778",
  "author": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3545-944X"
  },
  "description": "Depicts a fence at a disused motor racing venue with the front part of a",
  "encodingFormat": "image/jpeg",
  "exifData": [
    {
      "@id": "#2eb90b09-a8b8-4946-805b-8cba077a7137"
    },
    {
      "@id": "#c2521494-9b94-4b23-a713-6b281f540823"
    }
  ]
},
{
  "@id": "#c2521494-9b94-4b23-a713-6b281f540823",
  "@type": "PropertyValue",
  "name": "InternalSerialNumber",
  "value": "4102011002108002"
}
```

8.11 Places

To associate a Data Entity with a *Contextual Entity* representing a geographical location or region, the entity SHOULD have a property of `contentLocation` or `spatialCoverage` with a value of type `Place`.

To express point or shape geometry it is recommended that a `geo` property on a `Place` entity SHOULD link to a `Geometry` entity, with an `asWKT` property that expresses the point or shape in Well Known Text (WKT) format. This example is a point, `POINT ($longitude, $latitude)`, but other `asWKT` primitives, `LINESTRING` & `POLYGON` SHOULD be used as required.

This example shows how to define a place, using a geonames ID:

```

{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "...": "...",
  "contentLocation": {
    "@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/",
  "@type": "Place",
  "description": "Catalina Park is a disused motor racing venue, located at Katoomba ...",
  "geo": {
    "@id": "_:Geometry-1"
  },
  "identifier": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/",
  "url": "https://www.geonames.org/8152662/catalina-park.html",
  "name": "Catalina Park"
},
{
  "@id": "_:Geometry-1",
  "@type": "Geometry",
  "name": "Geometry-1",
  "asWKT": "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/1.3/CRS84> POINT (150.301195 -33.7152)"
}

```

Tip: To find the `@id` and `identifier` corresponding to a GeoNames HTML page like <https://www.geonames.org/8152662/catalina-park.html>, click its `.rdf` button to download the RDF metadata (<https://sws.geonames.org/8152662/about.rdf>). In the RDF metadata, find the line that looks like the following: `<gn:Feature rdf:about="http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/">`. The part in the quotes is the identifier (in this case, <http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/>).

Tip: Note the use of a JSON-LD blank node identifier here (starting with `_:`) - this indicates to an RO-Crate presentation application that the entity does not stand in its own right, and may be displayed inline (in this case as a map).

Tip: It is considered best practice to include the explicit mentioning of the CRS (Coordinate Reference System) identified through its `opengis` URI at the start of the `asWKT` field. This provides the essential context to have the numbers in the remainder of the string correctly be plotted on the map. Note, however, that many GIS related tools expect that information to be fed in via a separate configuration setting or API call. Handling these strings in any app that interacts with such systems might therefore require some extra processing.

Note: Any of the `schema.org` geographical classes and entities MAY be used on a `Place` element to describe geographical points and shapes, and previous versions of this specification did show examples of using latitude and longitude properties and entities such as `GeoCoordinates`. However, this results in very verbose JSON-LD, and there is some imprecision in the `Schema.org` specification that makes this approach hard to implement in applications for analysis

or presentation of RO-Crates. We found that developers were resorting to embedding escaped GeoJSON as string values in RO-Crate; instead of this, WKT format is more compact and easier to implement and is recommended for use in RO-Crate as shown above.

8.12 Subjects & keywords

Subject properties (equivalent to a Dublin Core Subject) on the root data entity or a data entity MUST use the about property.

Keyword properties MUST use keywords. Note that by Schema.org convention, keywords are given as a single JSON string, with individual keywords separated by commas.

```
{
  "keywords": "Gibraltar, Spain, British Overseas Territory, city, map",
  "about": { "@id": "http://dbpedia.org/resource/Gibraltar" }
}
```

8.13 Time

To describe the *time period* which an RO-Crate Data Entity (or the root data entity) is *about*, use temporalCoverage:

```
{
  "@id": "photos/",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "Photos of Gibraltar from 1950 till 1975",
  "about": {"@id": "http://dbpedia.org/resource/Gibraltar"},
  "temporalCoverage": "1950/1975"
}
```

8.14 Thumbnails

A File or any other entity MAY have a thumbnail property which references another file.

For example, the below RepositoryObject is related to four files which are all versions of the same image (via hasFile), one of which is a thumbnail. The thumbnail MUST be included in the RO-Crate.

If thumbnails are incidental to the data set, they need not be referenced by hasPart or hasFile relationships, but they must be in the BagIt manifest if in a *Bagged RO-Crate*.

```
{
  "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/items/383",
  "@type": [
    "RepositoryObject",
    "ImageObject"
  ],
  "identifier": [
    "ftf_photo_stapleton1"
  ]
}
```

```

],
"description": [
  "Photo of Eugenie Stapleton inside her home"
],
"license": [
  "Content in the Western Sydney Women's Oral History Project: From farms to freeways co
],
"publisher": [
  "University of Western Sydney"
],
"hasFile": [
  {
    "@id": "files/383/original_c0f1189ec13ca936e8f556161663d4ba.jpg"
  },
  {
    "@id": "files/383/fullsize_c0f1189ec13ca936e8f556161663d4ba.jpg"
  },
  {
    "@id": "files/383/thumbnail_c0f1189ec13ca936e8f556161663d4ba.jpg"
  },
  {
    "@id": "files/383/square_thumbnail_c0f1189ec13ca936e8f556161663d4ba.jpg"
  }
],
"thumbnail": [
  {
    "@id": "files/383/thumbnail_c0f1189ec13ca936e8f556161663d4ba.jpg"
  }
],
"name": [
  "Photo of Eugenie Stapleton 1"
],
"copyrightHolder": [
  { "@id": "https://westernsydney.edu.au"}
],
},
{
  "@type": "File",
  "@id": "files/384/original_2ebbe681aa6ec138776343974ce8a3dd.jpg"
},
{
  "@type": "File",
  "@id": "files/384/fullsize_2ebbe681aa6ec138776343974ce8a3dd.jpg"
},
{
  "@type": "File",
  "@id": "files/384/thumbnail_2ebbe681aa6ec138776343974ce8a3dd.jpg"
},
{
  "@type": "File",

```

```
"@id": "files/384/square_thumbnail_2ebbe681aa6ec138776343974ce8a3dd.jpg"
}
```

9 The focus of an RO-Crate

In addition to simple data packaging, RO-Crates may have a “main” entry point or topic (referenced with a singleton `mainEntity` property), or function as a bundle of one or more Contextual Entities referenced via the `mentions` property.

9.1 RO-Crates with a “main entity”

An RO-Crate may have a single main entity that is considered the point, or focus of the RO-Crate. This may be referenced from the *Root Data Entity* using the `mainEntity` property.

9.1.1 RO-Crates with a data entity as `mainEntity`

The focus of an RO-Crate may be a single *Data Entity* supplemented by other data and/or contextual entities.

For example, in the Workflow RO-Crate profile, the use of `mainEntity` singles-out the workflow file from supporting files.

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "Example Workflow",
  "description": "An example workflow RO Crate",
  "license": "Apache-2.0",
  "datePublished": "2023-01-01",
  "mainEntity": {
    "@id": "example_workflow.cwl"
  },
  "hasPart": [
    {
      "@id": "example_workflow.cwl"
    },
    {
      "@id": "diagram.svg"
    },
    {
      "@id": "README.md"
    }
  ]
}
```

9.1.2 RO-Crates with a contextual entity as `mainEntity`

The focus of the RO-Crate may be a description of a *Contextual Entity*, for example in an RO-Crate used in a repository or encyclopedia where a

`RepositoryObject` bundles together images and other files, but the main focus of the RO-Crate is on describing a person.

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": ["Dataset", "RepositoryObject"],
  "name": "Reibey, Mary (1777 - 1855)",
  "...": "...",
  "mainEntity": {
    "@id": "https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mary_Reibey"
  },
  "hasPart" : [
    {"@id": "photo1.jpg"},
    {"@id": "photo2.jpg"}
  ]
}

{
  "@id": "https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mary_Reibey",
  "@type": "Person",
  "name": "Mary Reibey",
  "description": "Mary Reibey née Haydock (12 May 1777 - 30 May 1855) was an English-born"
}
```

9.2 RO-Crates which focus on multiple *Contextual Entities*

RO-Crates may describe *Contextual Entities* which are linked to the Root Data Entity via `mentions` relationships.

For example, RO-Crates can be used as containers for Schema.org-style vocabularies (here also extending the RO-Crate JSON-LD context to define the namespace for `txc`):

```
{ "@context": [
  "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  {"txc": "https://purl.archive.org/language-data-commons/terms#"}
],
"@graph": [
  {
    "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
    "@type": "CreativeWork",
    "description": "RO-Crate Metadata File Descriptor (this file)",
    "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
    "about": {"@id": "./"}
  },
  {
    "@id": "./",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "description": "This is an experimental language data ontology based on OLAC terms f",
    "hasPart": [],
  }
]
```

```

    "name": "Language Data Ontology",
    "mentions": ["txc:Annotation", "txc:CollectionEvent"]
  },
  {
    "@id": "txc:Annotation",
    "@type": "rdfs:Class",
    "name": "Annotation",
    "sameAs": "http://www.language-archives.org/REC/type-20020628.html#annotation",
    "rdfs:comment": "The resource includes information which annotates some other lingu",
    "rdfs:label": "Annotation",
    "rdfs:subClassOf": {
      "@id": "schema:CreativeWork"
    }
  },
  {
    "@id": "txc:CollectionEvent",
    "@type": "rdfs:Class",
    "name": "CollectionEvent",
    "rdfs:comment": "A description of an event at which one or more PrimaryTexts were ca",
    "rdfs:label": "CollectionEvent",
    "rdfs:subClassOf": [
      {
        "@id": "schema:Event"
      },
      {
        "@id": "schema:CreateAction"
      }
    ]
  }
]
}

```

The following example shows how both `mainEntity` and `mentions` can be used together, in this case to describe a workflow with a test suite:

- the `mainEntity` is the workflow file, a *Data Entity*
- the test suite `#test1` is a *Contextual Entity* highlighted using `mentions`.

```

{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "sort-and-change-case",
  "description": "sort lines and change text to upper case",
  "license": "Apache-2.0",
  "mainEntity": {
    "@id": "sort-and-change-case.ga"
  },
  "mentions": [ {"@id": "#test1"} ],
  "hasPart": [
    {
      "@id": "sort-and-change-case.ga"
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    },
    {
      "@id": "test/test1/sort-and-change-case-test.yml"
    }
  ]
},
{
  "@id": "#test1",
  "name": "test1",
  "@type": "TestSuite",
  "instance": [
    {"@id": "#test1_1"}
  ],
  "definition": {"@id": "test/test1/sort-and-change-case-test.yml"}
},
{
  "@id": "#test1_1",
  "name": "test1_1",
  "@type": "TestInstance",
  "runsOn": {"@id": "#jenkins"},
  "url": "http://example.org/jenkins",
  "resource": "job/tests/"
},
{
  "@id": "test/test1/sort-and-change-case-test.yml",
  "@type": [
    "File",
    "TestDefinition"
  ],
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "#planemo"}
},
{
  "@id": "#jenkins",
  "@type": "TestService",
  "name": "Jenkins",
  "url": {"@id": "https://www.jenkins.io"}
},
{
  "@id": "#planemo",
  "@type": "SoftwareApplication",
  "name": "Planemo",
  "url": {"@id": "https://github.com/galaxyproject/planemo"},
  "version": ">=0.70"
}

```

10 Detailing provenance of entities

10.1 Equipment used to create files

To specify which **equipment** was used to create or update a Data Entity, the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* SHOULD have a *Contextual Entity* for each item of equipment which SHOULD be of `@type` `IndividualProduct`. The entity SHOULD have a serial number and manufacturer that identify the equipment as completely as possible. In the following case the equipment is a bespoke machine. The equipment SHOULD be described on a web page, and the address of the description SHOULD be used as its `@id`.

```
{
  "@id": "https://confluence.csiro.au/display/ASL/Hovermap",
  "@type": "IndividualProduct",
  "description": "The CSIRO bentwing is an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV, commonly known as",
  "identifier": "https://confluence.csiro.au/display/ASL/Hovermap",
  "name": "Bentwing"
}
```

Use the `CreateAction` and `UpdateAction` types to model the contributions of *Contextual Entities* of type `Person` or `Organization` in the creation of files.

In the example below, the `CreateAction` has a human agent, the object is a `Place` (a cave) and the `Hovermap` drone is the instrument used in the file creation event.

```
{
  "@id": "#DataCapture_wcc02",
  "@type": "CreateAction",
  "agent": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1672-552X"
  },
  "instrument": {
    "@id": "https://confluence.csiro.au/display/ASL/Hovermap"
  },
  "object": {
    "@id": "#victoria_arch"
  },
  "result": [
    {
      "@id": "wcc02_arch.laz"
    },
    {
      "@id": "wcc02_arch_traj.txt"
    }
  ]
},
{
  "@id": "#victoria_arch",
  "@type": "Place",
  "address": "Wombeyan Caves, NSW 2580",
  "name": "Victoria Arch"
}
```

```
}
```

10.2 Software used to create files

To specify which software was used to create or update a file, the software application SHOULD be represented with an entity of type `SoftwareApplication`, with a version property, e.g. from `tool --version`.

For example:

```
{
  "@id": "https://www.imagemagick.org/",
  "@type": "SoftwareApplication",
  "url": "https://www.imagemagick.org/",
  "name": "ImageMagick",
  "version": "ImageMagick 6.9.7-4 Q16 x86_64 20170114 http://www.imagemagick.org"
}
```

The software SHOULD be associated with the File(s) (or other data entities) it created as an instrument of a `CreateAction`, with the File referenced by a result property. Any input files SHOULD be referenced by the object property.

In the below example, an image with the `@id` of `pics/2017-06-11%2012.56.14.jpg` was transformed into a new image `pics/sepia_fence.jpg` using the *ImageMagick* software application as “instrument”. Actions MAY have human-readable names, which MAY be machine generated for use at scale.

```
{
  "@id": "#Photo_Capture_1",
  "@type": "CreateAction",
  "agent": {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3545-944X"
  },
  "description": "Photo snapped on a photo walk on a misty day",
  "endTime": "2017-06-11T12:56:14+10:00",
  "instrument": [
    {
      "@id": "#EPL1"
    },
    {
      "@id": "#Panny20mm"
    }
  ],
  "result": {
    "@id": "pics/2017-06-11%2012.56.14.jpg"
  }
},
{
  "@id": "#Sepia_Conversion_1",
  "@type": "CreateAction",
  "name": "Convert dog image to sepia",
  "description": "convert -sepia-tone 80% test_data/sample/pics/2017-06-11\\ 12.56.14.jpg"
}
```

```

    "endTime": "2018-09-19T17:01:07+10:00",
    "instrument": {
      "@id": "https://www.imagemagick.org/"
    },
    "object": {
      "@id": "pics/2017-06-11%2012.56.14.jpg"
    },
    "result": {
      "@id": "pics/sepia_fence.jpg"
    }
  }
}

```

Tip: If representing command lines, double escape `\\` so that JSON preserves the `\` character.

If multiple `SoftwareApplications` have been used in composition, such as from a script or workflow, then the `CreateAction`'s `instrument` SHOULD rather reference a `SoftwareSourceCode` which can be further described as explained in the `Workflows and scripts` section.

10.3 Recording changes to RO-Crates

To record an action which changes an entity's metadata, or changes its state in a publication or other workflow, a `CreateAction` or `UpdateAction` SHOULD be associated with a `Data Entity` or, for the RO-Crate itself, with the root data entity.

A `curation Action` MUST have at least one object which associates it with either the root data entity `Dataset` or one of its components.

An `Action` which creates new *Data entities* - for example, the creation of a new metadata file - SHOULD have these as results.

An `Action` SHOULD have a name and MAY have a description.

An `Action` SHOULD have an `endTime`, which MUST be in ISO 8601 date format and SHOULD be specified to at least the precision of a day. An `Action` MAY have a `startTime` meeting the same specifications.

An `Action` SHOULD have a human agent who was responsible for authorizing the action, and MAY have an `instrument` which associates the action with a particular piece of software (for example, the content management system or data catalogue through which an update was approved) which SHOULD be of `@type SoftwareApplication`.

An `Action`'s status MAY be recorded in an `actionStatus` property. The status must be one of the values enumerated by `ActionStatusType`: `ActiveActionStatus`, `CompletedActionStatus`, `FailedActionStatus` or `PotentialActionStatus`.

An `Action` which has failed MAY record any error information in an `error` property.

`UpdateAction` SHOULD only be used for actions which affect the `Dataset` as a whole, such as movement through a workflow.

To record curation actions which modify a File within a Dataset - for example, by correcting or enhancing metadata - the old version of the File SHOULD be retained, and a CreateAction added which has the original version as its object and the new version as its result.

```
{
  "@id": "#history-01",
  "@type": "CreateAction",
  "object": { "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009240" },
  "name": "R0-Crate created",
  "endTime": "2018-08-31",
  "agent": { "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5152-5307" },
  "instrument": { "@id": "https://stash.research.uts.edu.au" },
  "actionStatus": { "@id": "http://schema.org/CompletedActionStatus" }
},

{
  "@id": "#history-02",
  "@type": "UpdateAction",
  "object": { "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009240" },
  "name": "R0-Crate published",
  "endTime": "2018-09-10",
  "agent": { "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5152-5307" },
  "instrument": { "@id": "https://stash.research.uts.edu.au" },
  "actionStatus": { "@id": "http://schema.org/CompletedActionStatus" }
},

{
  "@id": "#history-03",
  "@type": "CreateAction",
  "object": { "@id": "metadata.xml.v0.1" },
  "result": { "@id": "metadata.xml" },
  "name": "metadata update",
  "endTime": "2018-09-12",
  "agent": { "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5152-5307" },
  "instrument": { "@id": "https://stash.research.uts.edu.au" },
  "actionStatus": { "@id": "http://schema.org/CompletedActionStatus" }
},

{
  "@id": "#history-04",
  "@type": "UpdateAction",
  "object": { "@id": "https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009240" },
  "name": "R0-Crate published",
  "endTime": "2018-09-13",
  "agent": { "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5152-5307" },
  "instrument": { "@id": "https://stash.research.uts.edu.au" },
  "actionStatus": { "@id": "http://schema.org/FailedActionStatus" },
  "error": "Record is already published"
},
```

```

{
  "@id": "https://stash.research.uts.edu.au",
  "@type": "IndividualProduct",
  "name": "Stash",
  "description": "UTS Research Data Catalogue",
  "identifier": "https://stash.research.uts.edu.au"
}

```

10.4 Digital Library and Repository content

To describe an export from a Digital Library or repository system, RO-Crate uses the *Portland Common Data Model* (PCDM).

A Contextual Entity from a repository, representing an abstract entity such as a person, or a work, or a place SHOULD have a `@type` of `RepositoryObject`, in addition to any other types.

Objects MAY be grouped together in `RepositoryCollections` with `hasMember` pointing to the `RepositoryObject`.

Note: The terms `RepositoryObject` and `RepositoryCollection` are renamed in RO-Crate to avoid collision between other vocabularies and the PCDM terms `Collection` and `Object`. The term `RepositoryFile` is renamed to avoid clash with RO-Crate's `File` mapping to `http://schema.org/MediaObject`.

Warning :PCDM specifies that files should have only technical metadata, not descriptive metadata, which is *not* a restriction in RO-Crate. If the RO-Crate is to be imported into a strict PCDM repository, modeling of object/file relationships will be necessary.

For example, this data is exported from an Omeka repository:

```

{
  "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/collections/6",
  "@type": "RepositoryCollection",
  "title": "Project Materials",
  "description": [
    "Materials associated with the project, including fliers seeking participants, lists
  ],
  "publisher": {"@id": "University of Western Sydney"},
  "rights": "Copyright University of Western Sydney 2015",
  "hasMember": [
    {
      "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/items/166"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/items/167"
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/items/168"
    }
  ],
}

```

```

    {
      "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/items/169"
    }
  ]
},
{
  "@id": "https://omeka.uws.edu.au/farmstofreeways/api/items/166",
  "@type": "RepositoryObject",
  "title": [
    "Western Sydney Women's Oral History Project: Flier (illustrated)"
  ],
  "description": [
    "Flier (illustrated) seeking participants for the project."
  ],
  "publisher": { "@id": "https://westernsydney.edu.au"},
  "rights": "Copyright University of Western Sydney 2015",
  "originalFormat": "Paper",
  "identifier": "FTF_flier_illust",
  "rightsHolder": [
    "Western Sydney University"
  ],
  "license": {
    "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/au/"
  },
  "hasFile": [
    {
      "@id": "content/166/original_eece70f73bf8979c0bcfb97065948531.pdf"
    },
    ...
  ]
},
{
  "@type": "File",
  "@id": "content/166/original_eece70f73bf8979c0bcfb97065948531.pdf"
}

```

11 RO-Crate profiles

While RO-Crates can be considered general-purpose containers of arbitrary data and open-ended metadata, in practical use within a particular domain, application or framework, it will be beneficial to further constrain RO-Crate to a specific **profile**: a set of conventions, types and properties that one can minimally require and expect to be present in that subset of RO-Crates.

Defining and conforming to such a profile enables reliable programmatic consumption of an RO-Crate's content, as well as consistent creation, e.g. via a form in a user interface containing the required types and properties. Likewise, a rendering of an RO-Crate can more easily make rich UI components if it can reliably assume, for instance, that a **Person** always has an **affiliation** to a

Organization which has a `url` - a restriction that may not be appropriate for all types of RO-Crates.

As such, RO-Crate profiles can be considered a *duck typing* mechanism for RO-Crates, but also as a classifier to indicate the crate's purpose, expectations, and focus.

11.1 Publishing an RO-Crate profile

An *RO-Crate profile* is identified with a **profile URI** with the following constraints:

- The profile URI **MUST** resolve to a human-readable *profile description* (e.g. a HTML web page)
 - The profile URI **MAY** have a corresponding machine-readable *Profile Crate*
- The profile URI **SHOULD** be a *permalink* (persistent identifier)
 - e.g. starting with `https://w3id.org/` `http://purl.org/` or `https://doi.org/`
- The profile URI **SHOULD** be *versioned* with MAJOR.MINOR, e.g. `http://example.com/image-profile-2`

The profile description declares the set of conventions to be used.

- The profile description **SHOULD** use key words **MUST**, **MUST NOT**, **REQUIRED**, **SHALL**, **SHALL NOT**, **SHOULD**, **SHOULD NOT**, **RECOMMENDED**, **MAY**, and **OPTIONAL** as described in RFC 2119.
- The profile **MAY** require/suggest which **@type** of data entities and/or contextual entities are expected.
- The profile **MAY** require/suggest *properties* expected per type of entity (e.g. “*Each CreativeWork MUST declare a license*”)
- The profile **MAY** require/suggest a particular version of RO-Crate.
- The profile **MAY** recommend RO-Crate extensions with domain-specific terms and vocabularies.
- The profile **MAY** require/suggest a particular JSON-LD context.
- The profile **MAY** require/suggest a particular RO-Crate publishing method or packaging like `.zip` or `BagIt`.

11.2 Declaring conformance of an RO-Crate profile

RO-Crates that are *conforming to* (or intending to conform to) such a profile **SHOULD** declare this using `conformsTo` on the Root Data Entity:

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "conformsTo":
    [{"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4"}]
}
```

It is valid for a crate to conform to multiple profiles, in which case `conformsTo` is an unordered array.

Note: Profile conformance is declared on the *Root Data Entity* (`./`)

in this example), rather than on the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* (`ro-crate-metadata.json`) where conformance to the base RO-Crate specification is declared. This is because the profile applies to the whole RO-Crate, and may cover aspects beyond the crate's metadata file (e.g. identifiers, packaging, purpose).

Each profile listed in `conformsTo` on the *Root Data Entity* MUST link to a corresponding contextual entity for the profile, for example:

```
{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4",
  "@type": ["CreativeWork", "Profile"],
  "name": "Process Run crate profile",
  "version": "0.4.0"
}
```

In the contextual entity for a profile:

- The `@type` SHOULD be an array.
- The `@type` MUST include `Profile`.
- The `@type` SHOULD include `CreativeWork` (indicating a Web Page) or `Dataset` (indicating a Profile Crate).
- The entity SHOULD have an absolute URI as `@id`
- The entity SHOULD have a descriptive name
- The entity MAY declare version, preferably according to Semantic Versioning

11.3 Profile Crate

While the Profile URI `@id` MUST resolve to a human-readable *profile description*, it MAY additionally be made to resolve to a *Profile Crate*.

A **Profile Crate** is a type of RO-Crate that represents an RO-Crate profile. It gathers resources which further define the profile in addition to the *profile description*. This allows formalizing an alternative profile description for machine-readability (for instance for validation), and also additional resources like examples. The rest of this subsection declares the content of this Profile Crate.

The Profile Crate `@id` declared within its own RO-Crate Metadata Document SHOULD be an absolute URI, and the corresponding reference from its RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor updated accordingly. If the URI is a permanent URI, it SHOULD also be set as the `identifier`.

Within the Profile Crate, its Root Data Entity MUST declare `Profile` as an additional `@type`:

```
{
  "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
  "about": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4"}
},
{
```

```

    "@id": "ro-crate-preview.html",
    "@type": "CreativeWork",
    "about": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4" }
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4",
    "@type": ["Dataset", "Profile"],
    "name": "Process Run crate profile",
    "version": "0.4.0",
    "isProfileOf": [
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3" }
    ],
    "hasPart": [
      { "@id": "index.html" }
    ],
    "hasResource": [
      { "@id": "#hasSpecification" }
    ],
    "...": ""
  },
  {
    "@id": "index.html",
    "@type": "File",
    "name": "Process Run crate profile description",
    "encodingFormat": "text/html",
    "about": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4",
  },
  {
    "@id": "#hasSpecification",
    "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
    "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prop/role/specification" },
    "hasArtifact": { "@id": "index.html" }
  }
}

```

The earlier requirements for a Profile entity also apply here. In addition, in a Profile Crate the *Root Data Entity*:

- MUST reference the human-readable *profile description* as a data entity using `hasPart`
- SHOULD have an absolute URI as `@id`
- SHOULD have a descriptive name
- MAY declare version, preferably according to Semantic Versioning (e.g. 0.4.0)
- SHOULD reference the minimally expected RO-Crate specification as `isProfileOf`, which MAY be declared as contextual entity
- SHOULD list related data entities using `hasPart` (see below)
- MAY list profile descriptors using `hasResource` (see below)

Tip: The base RO-Crate specification referenced by `isProfileOf` is a Profile Crate itself, see `ro-crate-metadata.json` or `ro-crate-preview.html`.

11.3.1 How to retrieve a Profile Crate

To resolve a profile URI to a machine-readable *Profile Crate*, follow the approaches of retrieving an RO-Crate.

If none of these approaches worked, then this profile probably does not have a corresponding Profile Crate. For human display of the profile (e.g. when listing profiles another RO-Crate conforms to), display a hyperlink to its `@id` Web page, described by its `name`.

11.3.1.1 Shared contextual entities from a Profile Crate If an RO-Crate declares conformance to a given Profile Crate with `conformsTo` on its root data entity, contextual entities declared in the corresponding Profile Crate do *not* need to be repeated in the conforming crate.

For instance, if a Profile Crate adds a `DefinedTerm` entity according to the ad-hoc definitions, the term MAY be referenced in the conforming crate without making a contextual entity there. For archival purposes it MAY however still be preferable to copy such entities across to each conforming crate.

It is RECOMMENDED that `@id` of such shared entities are absolute URIs on both sides to avoid resolving relative paths, and the profile's recommended JSON-LD Context used by conforming crates SHOULD have a mapping to the URIs, see section Extending RO-Crate.

Note: In the conforming crate, any terms defined in the profile using `DefinedTerm`, `rdfs:Class` and `rdf:Property` MUST either be used as full URIs matching the `@id`, or mapped to these URIs from the conforming crate's JSON-LD `@context`. Note that JSON-LD only expands keys from `@id` and `@type`.

11.3.1.2 Archiving Profile Crates For archival purposes, a crate declaring profile conformance MAY choose to include a snapshot copy of the Profile Crate, indicated using `distribution`, as detailed for dataset distributions:

```
{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4",
  "@type": ["CreativeWork", "Profile"],
  "name": "Process Run crate profile",
  "version": "0.4.0",
  "distribution": { "@id": "process-profile-0.1.zip" }
},
{
  "@id": "process-profile-0.1.zip",
  "@type": "DataDownload",
  "encodingFormat": ["application/zip", {"@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRO"},
  "conformsTo": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate" }
}
```

This is mainly beneficial if the crate relies heavily on the profile, e.g. for definitions of terms.

11.3.2 What is included in the Profile Crate?

This section defines the type of resources that should or may be included in the Profile Crate for different purposes (roles).

11.3.2.1 Declaring the role within the crate In order for programmatic use of the Profile Crate to consume particular subresources, e.g. for validation, the *role* of each entity SHOULD be declared by including them using `hasResource` to a `ResourceDescriptor` contextual entity that references the subresource using `hasArtifact`, as defined by the Profiles Vocabulary:

```
{
  "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
  "about": {"@id": "http://example.com/my-crate-profile/0.1/"},
},
{
  "@id": "http://example.com/my-crate-profile/0.1/",
  "@type": ["Dataset", "Profile"],
  "name": "My Crate Profile",
  "version": "0.1.0",
  "hasPart": [
    {"@id": "http://example.com/my-crate-profile/0.1/shape.shex"}
  ],
  "hasResource": [
    {"@id": "#hasShape"}
  ]
},
{
  "@id": "#hasShape",
  "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
  "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/constraints" },
  "hasArtifact": {"@id": "http://example.com/my-crate-profile/0.1/shape.shex"}
}
```

The `ResourceDescriptor` entity MAY also declare `dct:format` or `dct:conformsTo`, however the data entity referenced with `hasArtifact` SHOULD always declare `encodingFormat` (with OPTIONAL `conformsTo`) to specify its encoding format, e.g.:

```
{
  "@id": "http://example.com/my-crate-profile/0.1/shape.shex",
  "@type": "File",
  "encodingFormat": [
    "text/shex",
    {"@id": "http://shex.io/shex-semantic/" }
  ]
}
```

The referenced role does not need to be declared as a `DefinedTerm` contextual entity unless it differs from these recommended predefined roles:

```

{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/constraints",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Constraints",
  "description": "Descriptions of obligations, limitations or extensions that the profil
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/example",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Example",
  "description": "Sample instance data conforming to the profile"
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/guidance",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Guidance",
  "description": "Documents, in human-readable form, how to use the profile"
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/mapping",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Mapping",
  "description": "Describes conversions between two specifications"
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/schema",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Schema",
  "description": "Machine-readable structural descriptions of data defined by the profil
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/specification",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Specification",
  "description": "Defining the profile in human-readable form"
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/validation",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Validation",
  "description": "Supplies instructions about how to verify conformance of data to the p
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/vocabulary",
  "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
  "name": "Vocabulary",
  "description": "Defines terms used in the profile specification"
},
{
  "@id": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo",

```

```

    "@type": ["DefinedTerm", "ResourceRole"],
    "name": "Conforms to",
    "description": "Suggestion of additional profile to conform to"
  }
}

```

The examples in the rest of this section will list the data entities with a corresponding `ResourceDescriptor` entity, but for brevity the required `hasPart` and `hasResource` references from the *Root Data Entity* will not be repeated.

Below follows the suggested data entities to include in a Profile Crate using `hasPart` and, if applicable, a corresponding `hasResource` to a `ResourceDescriptor`:

11.3.2.2 Profile description entity A Profile Crate MUST declare a human-readable *profile description*, which is about this Profile Crate and SHOULD have `encodingFormat` as `text/html`. The corresponding `ResourceDescriptor` SHOULD have identifier `http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/specification` or `http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/guidance` – for example:

```

{
  "@id": "index.html",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Process Run Crate profile description",
  "encodingFormat": "text/html",
  "about": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4",
},
{
  "@id": "#hasSpecification",
  "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
  "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/specification" },
  "hasArtifact": {"@id": "index.html"}
}

```

The *profile description* MAY (instead of say a dedicated `index.html` as above) be equivalent to the RO-Crate Website entity `ro-crate-preview.html` (promoting it to a data entity by listing it under `hasPart`):

```

{
  "@id": "#hasSpecification",
  "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
  "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/specification" },
  "hasArtifact": {"@id": "ro-crate-preview.html"}
},
{
  "@id": "ro-crate-preview.html",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "name": "RO-Crate preview of the Process Run Crate profile",
  "encodingFormat": "text/html",
  "about": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4"
}

```

11.3.2.3 Profile Schema entity An optional machine-readable *schema* of the profile, for instance a Describo JSON profile:

```
{
  "@id": "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/UTS-eResearch/describo/v0.13.0/src/component",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "PARADISEC profile for Describo",
  "encodingFormat": "application/json",
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://github.com/UTS-eResearch/describo/wiki/dsp-index#profil"},
},
{
  "@id": "#hasSchema",
  "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
  "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/schema" },
  "hasArtifact": {"@id": "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/UTS-eResearch/describo/v0.13"},
},
{
  "@id": "https://github.com/UTS-eResearch/describo/wiki/dsp-index#profile-structure",
  "@type": "Profile",
  "name": "Describo JSON profile"
}
}
```

A schema may formalize restrictions on the RO-Crate Metadata Document on a graph-level (e.g. what types/properties) as well as serialization level (e.g. use of JSON arrays).

This interpretation of *schema* assumes the resource somewhat describes the data structure, e.g. expected types and attributes in the RO-Crate's JSON-LD. Use alternatively the role <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/validation> if the schema is primarily a set of constraints for validation purposes, or <http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/vocabulary> for ontologies and term listings.

Below are known schema types and their recommended media type, with suggested identifiers for the contextual entities of `encodingFormat` with type `Standard` and `conformsTo` with type `Profile`:

Name	Media Type	encodingFormat URI	conformsTo URI
JSON Schema	application/json	https://www.jsonschema.org/draft/2020-12/schema	
Crate-O	application/json	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/817	https://github.com/Language-Research-Technology/ro-crate-editor-profiles
Describo	application/json	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/817	https://github.com/describo/profiles

Name	Type	encodingFormat Media URI	conformsTo URI
CheckMyCrate	application/json	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/817	https://github.com/KockataEPich/CheckMyCrate#profiles
SHACL	text/turtle	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/874	https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/
ShExC	text/shex	http://shex.io/shex- semantics/#shexc	
ShExJ	application/json	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/880	http://shex.io/shex- semantics/#shexj
BagIt Profile	application/json	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/817	https://bagit- profiles.github.io/bagit- profiles-specification/
SKOS	text/turtle	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/874	http://www.w3.org/TR/skos- reference
OWL 2 (in RDF)	text/turtle	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/874	http://www.w3.org/TR/ow l2-mapping-to-rdf/

Tip: Some of the above schema languages are based on general data structure syntaxes like `application/json` and `text/turtle`, and therefore have a generic `encodingFormat` with a specialized `conformsTo URI`, which itself is declared as a Profile.

11.3.2.4 Software that works with the profile Software that may consume/validate/generate RO-Crates following this profile (potentially using the schema):

```
{
  "@id": "https://arkisto-platform.github.io/describo/",
  "@type": "SoftwareApplication",
  "name": "Describo",
  "version": "0.13.0",
  "url": "https://arkisto-platform.github.io/describo/"
}
```

11.3.2.5 Repositories that expect the profile A repository or collection within a repository that may accept/contain RO-Crates following this profile:

```
{
  "@id": "https://mod.paradisec.org.au/",
  "@type": "RepositoryCollection",
  "title": "Modern PARADISEC demonstrator",
  "description": "PARADISEC curates digital material about small or endangered languages"
```

```

    "publisher": {"@id": "https://paradisec.org.au/"}
}

```

11.3.2.6 BagIt packaging If conforming RO-Crates should be packaged according to a BagIt profile (e.g. must be serialized as an `application/zip`):

```

{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/bagit/profile/0.3",
  "@type": "Profile",
  "name": "BagIt profile for RO-Crate in ZIP",
  "encodingFormat": [
    "application/json",
    {"@id": "https://bagit-profiles.github.io/bagit-profiles-specification/"}
  ]
}

```

11.3.2.7 Extension vocabularies A profile that extends RO-Crate SHOULD indicate which vocabulary/ontology it uses as a `DefinedTermSet`:

```

{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/test#",
  "@type": "DefinedTermSet",
  "name": "Namespace for workflow testing metadata",
  "url": "https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-terms/tree/master/test",
},
{
  "@id": "#hasTestVocabulary",
  "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
  "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/prof/role/vocabulary" },
  "hasArtifact": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/test#"}
}

```

The `@id` of the vocabulary SHOULD be the *namespace*, while `url` SHOULD go to a human-readable description of the vocabulary.

A profile that defines many extensions terms MAY define its own `DefinedTermSet` and relate the terms using `hasDefinedTerm`:

```

{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "identifier": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate",
  "name": "Common Provenance Model RO-Crate profiles and vocabulary",
  "hasPart": [
    { "@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#" }
  ],
  "hasResource": [
    { "@id": "#hasCPMVocabulary" }
  ]
},
{
  "@id": "#hasCPMVocabulary",

```

```

    "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
    "hasRole": { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/dx/role/vocabulary" },
    "hasArtifact": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#"}
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#",
    "@type": "DefinedTermSet",
    "name": "Namespace for Common Provenance Model RO-Crate model",
    "hasDefinedTerm": [
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#CPMProvenanceFile" },
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#CPMMetaProvenanceFile" }
    ]
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#CPMProvenanceFile",
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "..." : ""
  }
}

```

11.3.2.8 Extension terms A profile that extends RO-Crate MAY indicate particular terms directly as `DefinedTerm`, `rdfs:Class` and/or `rdf:Property` instances:

```

{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/test#runs0n",
  "@type": "DefinedTerm",
  "termCode": "runs0n",
  "name": "Runs on",
  "description": "Service where the test instance is executed",
  "url": "https://lifemonitor.eu/workflow_testing_ro_crate#test-instance"
}

```

The `termCode` SHOULD be valid as a key in JSON-LD `@context` of conforming RO-Crates. The term SHOULD be mapped to the terms' `@id` in the `@context` of this Profile Crate.

11.3.2.9 JSON-LD Context A profile that have a corresponding JSON-LD `@context` (e.g. to map its extensions terms, or to suggest a version of RO-Crate's official context) SHOULD indicate the context in the Profile Crate:

```

{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "name": "RO-Crate JSON-LD Context",
  "encodingFormat": "application/ld+json",
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#Context"},
  "version": "1.3.0"
},
{
  "@id": "http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#Context",
  "@type": "DefinedTerm",

```

```

    "name": "JSON-LD Context",
    "url": "https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/"
  }

```

An entity representing a JSON-LD context:

- MUST have an `encodingFormat` of `application/ld+json`
- MUST have an absolute URI as `@id`, which MUST be retrievable as JSON-LD directly or with content-negotiation and/or HTTP redirects.
- SHOULD have a *permalink* (persistent identifier) as `@id`
 - e.g. starting with `https://w3id.org/` `http://purl.org/`
- SHOULD use `https` rather than `http` with a certificate commonly accepted by browsers
- SHOULD have a `@id` URI that is *versioned* with MAJOR.MINOR, e.g. `https://example.com/image-profile-2.4`
- SHOULD have a descriptive name
- SHOULD have a `conformsTo` to the contextual entity `http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#Context`
- MAY declare version according to Semantic Versioning
- Including the `DefinedTerm` for JSON-LD is optional.

When updating a JSON-LD context in a Profile Crate:

- Updates MAY add new terms or patch fixes (with corresponding `version` change in the RO-Crate metadata)
- Updates SHOULD NOT remove terms already published and potentially used by consumers of the profile
- Updates SHOULD NOT replace URIs terms map to – except for typos.

Note that the referenced context URI does *not* have to match the `@context` of the Profile Crate itself.

Tip: The `@context` MAY be the Profile Crate’s Metadata JSON-LD file itself, if it is resolvable as media type `application/ld+json` over HTTP. Make sure the crate includes the defined terms both within its `@context` and ideally as entities in its `@graph`.

11.3.2.10 Multiple profiles RO-Crate profiles sometimes build on each other. Note that unlike traditional object-oriented programming with strict class hierarchies, profiles are a looser construct of conventions rather than absolute rules. RO-Crate therefore does not enforce any particular “inheritance” across profiles.

An RO-Crate conforming to multiple RO-Crate profiles SHOULD explicitly declare `conformsTo` for each profile. Each profile listed MUST have a corresponding contextual entity.

A Profile Crate can *suggest* interoperable profiles under `hasPart`, and recommend them by using the role `http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo` in a resource descriptor. For example, the Workflow Run Crate profile recommends two other profiles, the “parent” Process Run Crate and a “mix-in” Workflow RO-Crate:

```

{
  "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/workflow/0.4",

```

```

    "@type": ["Dataset", "Profile"],
    "name": "Workflow Run crate profile",
    "description": "Profile for recording a workflow run. It is recommended to also conform",
    "version": "0.4.0",
    "isProfileOf": [
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3" },
    ],
    "hasPart": [
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4" },
      { "@id": "https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0" },
      { "...": "" }
    ],
    "hasResource": [
      { "@id": "#shouldConformToWorkflowROcrate" },
      { "@id": "#shouldConformToProcess" }
      { "...": "" }
    ],
    "...": ""
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4",
    "@type": ["CreativeWork", "Profile"],
    "name": "Process Run Crate profile",
    "version": "0.4.0"
  },
  {
    "@id": "https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0",
    "@type": ["CreativeWork", "Profile"],
    "name": "Workflow RO-Crate profile",
    "version": "1.0"
  },
  {
    "@id": "#shouldConformToWorkflowROcrate",
    "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
    "hasRole": { "@id": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo" },
    "hasArtifact": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0" }
  },
  {
    "@id": "#shouldConformToProcess",
    "@type": "ResourceDescriptor",
    "hasRole": { "@id": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo" },
    "hasArtifact": { "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/wfrun/process/0.4" }
  }
}

```

Note that this does not enforce any particular hierarchy of profiles, thus listed profiles can be both more general or more specific than the given Profile Crate. A given profile MAY provide further recommendations or requirements for how the related profiles are to be used in its human-readable documentation, e.g. by elaborating on the `ResourceDescriptor`.

It is NOT RECOMMENDED to include further elements of the referenced pro-

files, e.g. their `ResourceDescriptors`, see How to retrieve a Profile Crate.

12 Workflows and Scripts

Scientific workflows and scripts that were used (or can be used) to analyze or generate files contained in an RO-Crate MAY be embedded in an RO-Crate. See also the Provenance section on Software Used to Create Files.

Workflows and *scripts* SHOULD be described using data entities of type `SoftwareSourceCode`.

The distinction between `SoftwareSourceCode` and `SoftwareApplication` for software is fluid, and comes down to availability and understandability. For instance, office spreadsheet applications are generally available and do not need further explanation (`SoftwareApplication`); while a Python script that is customized for a particular data analysis might be important to understand deeper and should therefore be included as `SoftwareSourceCode` in the RO-Crate dataset.

12.1 Describing scripts and workflows

A script is a *Data Entity* which MUST have the following properties:

- `@type` is an array with at least `File` and `SoftwareSourceCode` as values
- `@id` is a File URI linking to the executable script
- `name`: a human-readable name for the script.

A workflow is a *Data Entity* which MUST have the following properties:

- `@type` is an array with at least `File`, `SoftwareSourceCode` and `ComputationalWorkflow` as values
- `@id` is a File URI linking to the workflow entry-point.
- `name`: a human-readable name for the workflow.

Short example describing a *script*:

```
{
  "@id": "scripts/analyse_csv.py",
  "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode"],
  "name": "Analyze CSV files",
  "programmingLanguage": {"@id": "https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-380/"}
}
```

Short example describing a *workflow*:

```
{
  "@id": "workflow/retropath.knime",
  "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode", "ComputationalWorkflow"],
  "author": {"@id": "#thomas"},
  "name": "RetroPath Knime workflow",
  "description": "Retrosynthesis workflow calculating chemical reactions",
  "license": {"@id": "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0"},
  "programmingLanguage": {"@id": "#knime"}
}
```

There is no strong distinction between a *script* and a *workflow*; many computational workflows are written in script-like languages, and many scripts perform a *pipeline* of steps.

Here are some indicators for when a script should be considered a *workflow*:

- It performs a series of steps (*pipeline*)
- The executed steps are mainly external tools or services
- The main work is performed by the steps (script is not algorithmic)
- The steps exchange data in a *dataflow*, typically file inputs/outputs
- The script has well-defined *inputs* and *outputs*, e.g. file arguments

Here are some counter-indicators for when a script might **not** be a workflow:

- The script contains mainly algorithms or logic
- Data is exchanged with services outside of the system, e.g. a SQL database
- The script relies on a particular state of the system (e.g. appends existing files)
- An interactive user interface that controls the actions

12.2 Workflow Runtime and Programming Language

Scripts written in a *programming language*, as well as workflows, generally need a *runtime*; in RO-Crate the runtime SHOULD be indicated using a liberal interpretation of `programmingLanguage`.

Note that the language and its runtime MAY differ (e.g. different C++ compilers), but for scripts and workflows, frequently the language and runtime are essentially the same, and thus the `programmingLanguage`, implied to be a `ComputerLanguage`, can also be described as an executable `SoftwareApplication`:

```
{
  "@id": "scripts/analyse_csv.py",
  "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode"],
  "name": "Analyze CSV files",
  "programmingLanguage": {"@id": "https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-380/"}
},
{
  "@id": "https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-380/",
  "@type": ["ComputerLanguage", "SoftwareApplication"],
  "name": "Python 3.8.0",
  "version": "3.8.0"
}
```

A *contextual entity* representing a `ComputerLanguage` and/or `SoftwareApplication` MUST have a name, url and version, which should indicate a known version the workflow/script was developed or tested with. `alternateName` MAY be provided if there is a shorter colloquial name, for instance “*R*” instead of “*The R Project for Statistical Computing*”.

It is possible to indicate *steps* that are executed as part of an `ComputationalWorkflow` or `Script`, by using `hasPart` to relate additional `SoftwareApplication` or nested `SoftwareSourceCode` contextual entities:

```

{
  "@id": "workflow/analyze.cwl",
  "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode", "ComputationalWorkflow"],
  "name": "CWL workflow to analyze CSV and make PNG",
  "programmingLanguage": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/cwl/v1.1/"},
  "hasPart": [
    {"@id": "scripts/analyse_csv.py"},
    {"@id": "https://www.imagemagick.org/"}
  ]
}

```

12.3 Workflow diagram/sketch

It can be beneficial to show a diagram or sketch to explain the script/workflow. This may have been generated from a workflow management system, or drawn manually as a diagram. This diagram MAY be included from the SoftwareSourceCode data entity by using `image`, pointing to an ImageObject data entity which is about the SoftwareSourceCode:

```

{
  "@id": "workflow/workflow.knime",
  "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode", "ComputationalWorkflow"],
  "name": "RetroPath2.0 workflow",
  "image": {"@id": "workflow/workflow.svg" }
},
{
  "@id": "workflow/workflow.svg",
  "@type": ["File", "ImageObject"],
  "encodingFormat": "image/svg+xml",
  "name": "Diagram of RetroPath2.0 workflow",
  "about": {"@id": "workflow/workflow.knime"}
}

```

The image file format SHOULD be indicated with `encodingFormat` using an IANA registered media type like `image/svg+xml` or `image/png`. Additionally a reference to a Pronom identifier SHOULD be provided, which MAY be described as an additional contextual entity to give human-readable name to the format:

```

{
  "@id": "workflow/workflow.svg",
  "@type": ["File", "ImageObject"],
  "encodingFormat": ["image/svg+xml", {"@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM"}],
  "name": "Diagram of RetroPath2.0 workflow",
  "about": {"@id": "workflow/workflow.knime"}
},
,
{
  "@id": "https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/fmt/92",
  "name": "Scalable Vector Graphics",
  "@type": ["WebPage", "Standard"]
}

```

A workflow diagram may still be provided even if there is no programmatic `SoftwareSourceCode` that can be executed (e.g. because the workflow was done by hand). In this case the sketch itself is a proxy for the workflow and SHOULD have an `about` property referring to the *Root Data Entity* as a whole (assuming the RO-Crate represents the outcome of a single workflow), or to other Data Entities otherwise:

```
{
  "@id": "workflow/workflow.svg",
  "@type": ["File", "ImageObject"],
  "encodingFormat": ["image/svg+xml"],
  "name": "Diagram of an ad hoc workflow",
  "about": {"@id": "./"}
}
```

12.4 Complying with Bioschemas Computational Workflow profile

Data entities representing *workflows* (`@type: ComputationalWorkflow`) SHOULD comply with the Bioschemas ComputationalWorkflow profile, where possible.

When complying with this profile, the workflow data entities MUST describe these properties and their related contextual entities: name, programmingLanguage, creator, dateCreated, license, sdPublisher, url, version.

The ComputationalWorkflow profile explains the above and lists additional properties that a compliant ComputationalWorkflow data entity SHOULD include: citation, contributor, creativeWorkStatus, description, funding, hasPart, isBasedOn, keywords, maintainer, producer, publisher, runtimePlatform, softwareRequirements, targetProduct

A data entity conforming to the ComputationalWorkflow profile SHOULD declare the versioned profile URI using the `conformsTo` property ¹:

```
{ "@id": "workflow/alignment.knime",
  "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode", "ComputationalWorkflow"],
  "conformsTo":
    {"@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/ComputationalWorkflow/1.0-RELEASE"},
  "..": ""
}
```

12.4.1 Describing inputs and outputs

The input and output *parameters* for a workflow or script can be given with `input` and `output` to FormalParameter contextual entities. Note that this entity type usually represents a *potential* input/output value in a reusable workflow, much like function parameter definitions in general programming.

¹This is a liberal interpretation of `conformsTo` as it is the *structured data* about the workflow (this JSON-LD object) that conforms to the ComputationalWorkflow profile, not the file content of a workflow data entity (`workflow/alignment.knime`). Instead of introducing a `sdConformsTo` similar to `sdPublisher`, we here follow the current Bioschemas convention of indicating profile conformance when the JSON-LD is embedded within HTML pages.

If complying with the Bioschemas FormalParameter profile, the *contextual entities* for FormalParameter, referenced by `input` or `output`, MUST describe name.

The Bioschemas FormalParameter profile explains the above and lists additional properties that can be used, including `description`, `valueRequired`, `defaultValue` and `identifier`.

A contextual entity conforming to the FormalParameter profile SHOULD declare the versioned profile URI using `conformsTo` e.g.:

```
{
  "@id": "#36aadbd4-4a2d-4e33-83b4-0cbf6a6a8c5b",
  "@type": "FormalParameter",
  "conformsTo":
    {"@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/FormalParameter/1.0-RELEASE"},
  "..": ""
}
```

Note: `input`, `output` and `FormalParameter` are at time of writing proposed by Bioschemas and not yet integrated in Schema.org.

12.5 Complete Workflow Example

The below is an example of an RO-Crate complying with the Bioschemas ComputationalWorkflow profile 1.0:

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "./"}
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "hasPart": [
        { "@id": "workflow/alignment.knime" }
      ]
    },
    {
      "@id": "workflow/alignment.knime",
      "@type": ["File", "SoftwareSourceCode", "ComputationalWorkflow"],
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/ComputationalWorkflow/1.0-RELEASE"
      },
      "name": "Sequence alignment workflow",
      "programmingLanguage": {"@id": "#knime"},
      "creator": {"@id": "#alice"},
      "dateCreated": "2020-05-23",
    }
  ]
}
```

```

"license": { "@id": "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0"},
"input": [
  { "@id": "#36aadbd4-4a2d-4e33-83b4-0cbf6a6a8c5b"}
],
"output": [
  { "@id": "#6c703fee-6af7-4fdb-a57d-9e8bc4486044"},
  { "@id": "#2f32b861-e43c-401f-8c42-04fd84273bdf"}
],
"sdPublisher": {"@id": "#workflow-repo"},
"url": "http://example.com/workflows/alignment",
"version": "0.5.0"
},
{
"@id": "#36aadbd4-4a2d-4e33-83b4-0cbf6a6a8c5b",
"@type": "FormalParameter",
"conformsTo": {
"@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/FormalParameter/1.0-RELEASE"
},
"name": "genome_sequence",
"valueRequired": true,
"additionalType": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/data_2977"},
"format": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_1929"}
},
{
"@id": "#6c703fee-6af7-4fdb-a57d-9e8bc4486044",
"@type": "FormalParameter",
"conformsTo": {
"@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/FormalParameter/1.0-RELEASE"
},
"name": "cleaned_sequence",
"additionalType": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/data_2977"},
"encodingFormat": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_2572"}
},
{
"@id": "#2f32b861-e43c-401f-8c42-04fd84273bdf",
"@type": "FormalParameter",
"conformsTo": {
"@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/FormalParameter/1.0-RELEASE"
},
"name": "sequence_alignment",
"additionalType": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/data_1383"},
"encodingFormat": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_1982"}
},
{
"@id": "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0",
"@type": "CreativeWork",
"name": "Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial Share Alike 4.0 International",
"alternateName": "CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0"
},
{

```

```

    "@id": "#knime",
    "@type": "ComputerLanguage",
    "name": "KNIME Analytics Platform",
    "alternateName": "KNIME",
    "url": "https://www.knime.com/whats-new-in-knime-41",
    "version": "4.1.3"
  },
  {
    "@id": "#alice",
    "@type": "Person",
    "name": "Alice Brown"
  },
  {
    "@id": "#workflow-repo",
    "@type": "Organization",
    "name": "Example Workflow repository",
    "url": "http://example.com/workflows/"
  },
  {
    "@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_1929",
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "name": "FASTA sequence format"
  },
  {
    "@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_1982",
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "name": "ClustalW alignment format"
  },
  {
    "@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_2572",
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "name": "BAM format"
  },
  {
    "@id": "http://edamontology.org/data_2977",
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "name": "Nucleic acid sequence"
  },
  {
    "@id": "http://edamontology.org/data_1383",
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",
    "name": "Nucleic acid sequence alignment"
  }
]
}

```

13 Appendixes

13.1 Contents

- Changelog
- Handling relative URI references
- Implementation Notes
- RO-Crate JSON-LD

14 APPENDIX: Implementation notes

14.1 Programming with JSON-LD

When implementing tools to work with RO-Crate it is not necessary to use JSON-LD software libraries, however, programmers should keep in mind the following:

- **RO-Crate JSON-LD has a flat structure**; every entity is a JSON object directly within the `@graph` array in the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*. A useful strategy when processing a crate is to build a look-up table and/or function so that entities can be found via their ID, for example provide a method such as `getEntity(id)` which returns an entity by its id or a `null` value if it's not there.
- **Code defensively**. Code should not assume that values will always be a String; values for properties may be single scalar values such as strings or integers ("2" or 2), or references to other entities such as `{"@id", "_:1"}` (where the referenced entity may or may not be described in the crate, see the point above about having a `getEntity()` method).
- **Read the *whole* specification**. The RO-Crate specification addresses common use cases individually, introducing aspects of the specification as in a progressive manner. Some key points, such as *entities may have more than one value for @type*, may not be apparent from a quick reading.

14.2 Combining with other packaging schemes

RO-Crates may co-exist with other packaging schemes, such as BagIt or ELN (Electronic Lab Notebook) using two general approaches; either (a) *adding* RO-Crate into a package as part of the payload or (b) *wrapping* another kind of package.

14.2.1 ELN examples

An "ELN" archive (with file extension `.eln`, see IANA assignment and specification), is a valid RO-Crate packaged in a certain way. It is a ZIP file that contains a folder, and this folder is the *RO-Crate Root* containing the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file. See Structure of the archive from the specification.

As such, when processing a `.eln` file, one needs to extract the ZIP archive, look for the only folder present at root directory of the ZIP archive, and process its

content as a normal RO-Crate.

14.2.2 BagIt examples

BagIt is described in RFC 8493:

[BagIt is] ... a set of hierarchical file layout conventions for storage and transfer of arbitrary digital content. A “bag” has just enough structure to enclose descriptive metadata “tags” and a file “payload” but does not require knowledge of the payload’s internal semantics. This BagIt format is suitable for reliable storage and transfer.

BagIt and RO-Crate have largely separate concerns - RO-Crate is focussed on rich metadata, the semantics of data, while BagIt is about reliable transfer.

14.2.2.1 Adding RO-Crate to BagIt RO-Crate can be combined with BagIt simply by placing the RO-Crate files within the BagIt payload (`data/`) directory.

```
<BagIt base directory>/
|  bagit.txt                # As per BagIt specification
|  bag-info.txt             # As per BagIt specification
|  manifest-<algorithm>.txt # As per BagIt specification
|  fetch.txt                # Optional, per BagIt Specification
|  data/                    # Payload: RO-Crate root directory
|    ro-crate-metadata.json # RO-Crate Metadata File MUST be present
|    ro-crate-preview.html  # RO-Crate Website homepage MAY be present
|    ro-crate-preview_files/ # MAY be present
|    [payload files and directories] # 1 or more SHOULD be present
```

The Bag declaration `bagit.txt` MUST be present, the main role of this file is to mark the folder as a bag according to RFC8493. The file SHOULD have this fixed content in UTF-8:

```
BagIt-version: 1.0
Tag-File-Character-Encoding: UTF-8
```

The *BagIt base directory* containing `bagit.txt` can have any name, and can be archived/transferred in any way, e.g. within a ZIP archive, SFTP or even be exposed on the web.

The manifest file contains file checksums; the BagIt specifications recommends SHA-512 as default algorithm, that is `manifest-sha512.txt` SHOULD be present.

The BagIt manifest file MUST list the checksum of *all* payload files in `data/` and its subdirectories. Where `data/` is also the RO-Crate Root the manifest therefore MUST include `ro-crate-metadata.json`:

```
41846747...ee71  data/ro-crate-metadata.json
e1105ed0...5e13  data/chipseq_20200910.json
37fd3a02...bb95  data/results/pipeline_info/design_reads.csv
```

Note: The SHA-512 checksums have been shortened in the above example.

Creating the manifest file without using BagIt tools/libraries can be done using the equivalent of:

```
$ find data -type f -print0 | xargs -0 sha512sum > manifest-sha512.txt
```

Similarly checking the payload directory:

```
$ sha512sum --quiet -c manifest-sha512.txt
data/chipseq_20200910.json: FAILED
data/ro-crate-metadata.json: FAILED
sha512sum: WARNING: 2 computed checksums did NOT match
```

The BagIt manifest complements the RO-Crate structure as it provide a complete listing of all payload files with cryptographically strong checksums, ensuring the crate has been fully archived/transferred, which the weak CRC-32 checksum (TCP/IP, ZIP, gzip) is insufficient to guarantee, particularly for large crates.

To ensure the manifest file itself is complete, it is RECOMMENDED to include its checksum in `tagmanifest-sha512.txt`:

```
b0556450...8802 bag-info.txt
000b27e3...c52e manifest-sha512.txt
```

Warning :The BagIt manifest is intended to detect "bit rot" and accidental damage, it does not provide proof the RO-Crate has not been deliberately tampered with, as a malicious actor can also update the checksums.

Guarding against such scenarios would require additional cryptographic measures, e.g.

```
gpg --detach-sign --armor --output tagmanifest-sha512.txt.asc
tagmanifest-sha512.txt in combination with a secure PGP key exchange or equivalent trust network.
```

14.2.2.1.1 Base URI in BagIt The arcp specification suggests how BagIt UUID identifiers can be used to calculate the base URI of a bag, see section Establishing a base URI inside a ZIP file. For this purpose it is RECOMMENDED that `bag-info.txt` includes a fresh UUID like:

```
External-Identifier: urn:uuid:24e51ca2-5067-4598-935a-dac4e327d05a
```

14.2.2.1.2 Referencing external files The BagIt `fetch` file MAY be used to reference files to be downloaded into particular `data/` paths to *complete* the bag. These files may be large, require authentication or otherwise inconvenient to transfer within the BagIt folder.

Example `fetch.txt` using Git LFS:

```
https://media.githubusercontent.com/.../SPT5_INPUT_R1.bigWig 963489 data/results/SPT5_INPUT_
```

BagIt tools can help complete the bag and verify the checksum of the downloaded files according to the manifest.

The RO-Crate contained in `data/` MAY describe the bag with data entities as if the bag was *complete*, even if the large file is not (yet) present:

```

{
  "@id": "results/SPT5_INPUT_R1.bigWig",
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Normalized SPT5_INPUT_R1 bigWig for genome browsers",
  "encodingFormat": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_3006"},
  "url": "https://media.githubusercontent.com/media/biocompute-objects/bco-ro-example-ch
}

```

It is RECOMMENDED that the `url` is provided in the data entity and consistent with the line in `fetch.txt` in case the RO-Crate is transferred outside its BagIt container.

The `fetch.txt` approach can also be useful where other files in the RO-Crate reference a downloadable file by relative paths within `data/`, even if this file is not itself described in the RO-Crate metadata.

14.2.2.1.3 Snapshots of external files As an alternative to the above, web-based data entities can be used in the RO-Crate:

```

{
  "@id": "https://media.githubusercontent.com/media/biocompute-objects/bco-ro-example-ch
  "@type": "File",
  "name": "Normalized SPT5_INPUT_R1 bigWig for genome browsers",
  "encodingFormat": {"@id": "http://edamontology.org/format_3006"}
}

```

The above data entity MAY be combined with `fetch.txt` in the BagIt base directory:

```
https://media.githubusercontent.com/.../SPT5_INPUT_R1.bigWig 963489 data/snapshots/SPT5_INPU
```

In this case the file `data/snapshots/SPT5_INPUT_R1.bigWig` may be present, but unknown by RO-Crate; BagIt contains a checksummed snapshot of the web resource. Compared with the first approach, the RO-Crate is here primarily pointing at a web resource which is allowed to change without causing a BagIt checksum error.

14.2.2.2 Example of wrapping a BagIt bag in an RO-Crate Alternatively, an RO-Crate can *wrap* a BagIt bag, so that the RO-Crate metadata is outside of the bag directory and can be changed without changing the payload's checksums.

```

<RO-Crate root directory>/
|   ro-crate-metadata.json   # RO-Crate Metadata File MUST be present
|   ro-crate-preview.html   # RO-Crate Website homepage MAY be present
|   ro-crate-preview_files/ # MAY be present
|   bag1/                   # "Wrapped" bag - could have any name
|     bagit.txt              # As per BagIt specification
|     bag-info.txt           # As per BagIt specification
|     manifest-<algorithm>.txt # As per BagIt specification
|     fetch.txt              # Optional, per BagIt Specification
|     data/
|       [payload files and directories] # 1 or more SHOULD be present

```

```
|         example.txt
```

A Data Entity describing `example.txt` in this scenario would have an `@id` of `bag1/data/example.txt`:

```
{
  "@id": "bag1/data/example.txt",
  "name": "Example file"
}
```

14.3 Repository-specific identifiers

Root Data Entities MAY include repository-specific identifiers, described using Contextual Entities using a `PropertyValue`, with a name that identifies the repository and the identifier as a value. The *same* identifier MAY be used in multiple different repositories and effectively namespaced using the **name** of the `PropertyValue`.

```
{
  "@id": "./",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "identifier": ["https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b", {"@id": "_:localid:my-repo:my-id"}]
}

{
  "@id": "_:localid:my-repo:my-id",
  "@type": "PropertyValue",
  "name": "my-repo",
  "value": "my-id"
}

{
  "@id": "_:localid:other-repo:https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b",
  "@type": "PropertyValue",
  "name": "other-repo",
  "value": "https://doi.org/10.4225/59/59672c09f4a4b"
}
```

15 APPENDIX: RO-Crate JSON-LD

It is not necessary to use JSON-LD tooling to generate or parse the *RO-Crate Metadata Document*, although JSON-LD tools may make it easier to conform to this specification, e.g. handling relative URIs. It is however RECOMMENDED to use JSON tooling to handle JSON syntax and escaping rules.

This appendix shows a brief JSON-LD introduction for complying with the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* requirements.

The example below shows the overall structure of a flattened, compacted *RO-Crate Metadata Document* where `@context` refers to the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context*, while `@graph` is a flat array of the entities that constitute this RO-Crate.

```

{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [

    {
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "./"},
      "description": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)"
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "name": "Example RO-Crate",
      "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
      "hasPart": [
        {"@id": "data1.txt"},
        {"@id": "data2.txt"}
      ]
    },

    {
      "@id": "data1.txt",
      "@type": "File",
      "description": "One of hopefully many Data Entities",
      "author": {"@id": "#alice"},
      "contentLocation": {"@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/" }
    },
    {
      "@id": "data2.txt",
      "@type": "File"
    },

    {
      "@id": "#alice",
      "@type": "Person",
      "name": "Alice",
      "description": "One of hopefully many Contextual Entities"
    },
    {
      "@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/",
      "@type": "Place",
      "name": "Catalina Park"
    }
  ]
}

```

Note: entities above have been shortened for brevity, see the individual sections for data entities and contextual entities.

The order of the `@graph` array is not significant. Above we see that the RO-Crate JSON-LD graph contains the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor*, the *Root Data Entity*, any *Data Entities* and any *Contextual Entities*.

15.1 Describing entities in JSON-LD

Properties of an entity can refer to another URI or entity by using the form `{"@id": "uri-reference"}` as in the example above, where the `author` property in the `File` entity refer to the `Person` entity, identified as `#alice`.

Identifiers in `@id` SHOULD be either a valid *absolute URI* like `http://example.com/`, or a *URI path* relative to the RO-Crate root directory. Although legal in JSON-LD, `@id` paths in RO-Crate SHOULD NOT use `../` to climb out of the *RO-Crate Root*, rather such references SHOULD be translated to absolute URIs. See also section *Core Metadata for Data Entities*.

Care must be taken to express any relative paths using `/` separator and escape special characters like space (`%20`). As JSON-LD supports *IRIs*, international characters in identifiers SHOULD be encoded in UTF-8 rather than %-escaped.

Because the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* is *flattened*, all described entities must be JSON objects as direct children of the `@graph` element rather than being nested under another object or array. Properties referencing entities must use a JSON object with `@id` as the only key, e.g. `"author": {"@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097"}`

If no obvious identifier is available for a contextual entity, an identifier local to the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* can be generated.

- If the entity has a `name` such as a `Person` for instance an `@id` starting with `#` SHOULD be used; `{"@id": "#alice"}` or `{"@id": "#ac0bd781-7d91-4cdf-b2ad-7305921c7650"}`.
- For un-named entities, such as a `Geometry` entity a *blank node* identifier (e.g. `_:alice`) SHOULD be used. The use of a *blank node* identifier SHOULD be taken as hint by RO-Crate presentation software to display the entity in-line, not as a separate entity with its own view, such as a page.

Multiple values and references can be represented using JSON arrays, as exemplified in `hasPart` above; however as the RO-Crate JSON-LD is in *compact form*, any single-element arrays like `"author": [{"@id": "#alice"}]` SHOULD be unpacked to a single value like `"author": {"@id": "#alice"}`.

15.2 RO-Crate JSON-LD Context

The main purpose of the `@context` is to relate JSON property keys and `@type` references to their Linked Data identifiers, which in RO-Crate is based primarily on `http://schema.org/` URIs.

In other uses of JSON-LD the context may perform more automatic or detailed mapping, but the RO-Crate JSON-LD `context` is deliberately flat, listing every property and type.

To find the full description of a particular property or type, follow its URI from the context. For instance, we can find within the context <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context> that `author` above is mapped to <http://schema.org/author>:

```
"author": "http://schema.org/author",
```

The *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context* may either be set by reference to <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context> or by value (merging the two documents).

Consider the below (simplified) example of *by reference* using a versioned permalink:

```
{ "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "description": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "./"}
    }
  ]
}
```

The above is equivalent to the following JSON-LD using an embedded context, by adding the subset of corresponding keys from the external `@context`:

```
{ "@context": {
  "CreativeWork": "http://schema.org/CreativeWork",
  "description": "http://schema.org/description",
  "conformsTo": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo",
  "about": "http://schema.org/about"
},
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "description": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
      "about": {"@id": "./"}
    }
  ]
}
```

Note that `conformsTo` is retained to indicate which version of RO-Crate specification the root data entity conforms to.

While the second form is more verbose, one advantage is that it is “archivable” as it does not require Internet access for retrieving the `@context` permalink. Tools consuming or archiving RO-Crate MAY replace by-reference `@context` URIs with an embedded context by using version-specific hard-coded contexts. See <https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-crate/releases> to download the JSON-LD contexts corresponding to each version of this specification.

To check which RO-Crate version is used (in terms of properties and types expected), clients SHOULD check the property `conformsTo` on the *RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor* rather than the value of `@context`.

RO-Crate consumers SHOULD NOT do the opposite substitution from an embedded context, but MAY use the JSON-LD flattening algorithm with *compaction* to a referenced *RO-Crate JSON-LD context* (see also notes on handling relative URI references below).

Tip: The JSON-LD flattening & compaction algorithms can be used to rewrite to a different `@context`, e.g. to `https://schema.org/docs/jsonldcontext.jsonld` or a different version of the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context*.

15.3 RO-Crate JSON-LD Media type

The media type `application/ld+json` for `ro-crate-metadata.json` will, when following this specification, comply with the flattened/compacted JSON-LD profiles as well as `https://w3id.org/ro/crate`, which may be indicated in a HTTP response as:

```
HEAD http://example.com/ro-123/ro-crate-metadata.json HTTP/1.1
```

```
HTTP/1.1 200 OK
```

```
Content-Type: application/ld+json; profile="http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#flattened http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#compacted"
```

Note that most web servers will however serve `*.json` as `Content-Type: application/json`.

Requesting the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* from a browser may also need permission through CORS header `Access-Control-Allow-Origin` (however extra care should be taken if the RO-Crates require access control).

To change the configuration of **Apache HTTPD 2**, add the following to `.htaccess` or equivalent config file:

```
<Files "ro-crate-metadata.json">
  ForceType 'application/ld+json;profile="http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#flattened http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#compacted"'

  Header set Access-Control-Allow-Origin *
  Header set Access-Control-Expose-Headers "Content-Length,Content-Range,Content-Type"
</Files>
```

For **NGINX**, try:

```
location ~ ro-crate-metadata.json$ {
    types { } default_type 'application/ld+json;profile="http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#flattened http://www.w3.org/ns/json-ld#compacted"'

    add_header 'Access-Control-Allow-Origin' '*';
    add_header 'Access-Control-Expose-Headers' 'Content-Length,Content-Range,Content-Type';
}
```

For **Content-Delivery Networks** (e.g. GitHub pages) a symbolic link to `ro-crate-metadata.jsonld` may help to create an alias that can be served as `application/ld+json`:

```
ln -s ro-crate-metadata.json ro-crate-metadata.jsonld
```

15.4 Extending RO-Crate

To extend RO-Crate, implementers SHOULD try to use existing <http://schema.org/> properties and classes and MAY use terms from other vocabularies and ontologies when this is not possible. In many cases, a liberal interpretation of an schema.org term can be sufficient, e.g. even if <https://schema.org/HowTo> is explained with an example of changing a tire, [HowTo](#) could also help explain a Linux shell script as a series of computational steps.

Any additional *terms* (properties and types) from outside schema.org MUST be added as keys to the `@context` in the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* (if not present) (or be defined by the JSON-LD context in other ways). To avoid duplicating the *RO-Crate JSON-LD Context* the `@context: []` array form SHOULD be used as shown below.

URIs in the `@context` SHOULD resolve to a useful human readable page. When this is not possible - for example if the URI resolves to an RDF ontology file, a human-readable URI SHOULD be provided as a `DefinedTerm` using a `sameAs` description.

For example. The `@id` URI <http://purl.org/ontology/bibo/interviewee> from the BIBO ontology intends to resolve to an ontology file, which is not useful for humans, however the HTML section <http://neologism.ecs.soton.ac.uk/bibo.html#interviewee> is human-readable. To read more about best practices for content negotiation of vocabularies, we refer the reader to [Best Practice Recipes for Publishing RDF Vocabularies](#).

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
    {"interviewee": "http://purl.org/ontology/bibo/interviewee"}],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "http://purl.org/ontology/bibo/interviewee",
      "@type": "DefinedTerm",
      "name": "interviewee",
      "sameAs": "http://neologism.ecs.soton.ac.uk/bibo.html#interviewee"
    }
  ]
}
```

When generating the *RO-Crate Website* from *RO-Crate JSON-LD*, the code MUST use a `sameAs` URI (if present) as a target for an explanatory link for the term instead of the Linked Data URI supplied in the `@context`.

Where there is no RDF ontology available, then implementors SHOULD attempt to provide context by creating stable web-accessible URIs to document properties and classes, for example, by linking to a page describing the term.

15.5 Adding new or ad hoc vocabulary terms

Context terms must ultimately map to HTTP(s) URIs which poses challenges for crate-authors wishing to use their own vocabularies.

RO-Crate provides some strategies to add a new term (`DefinedTerm`, `rdfs:Class` or `rdf:Property`) that is not in Schema.org or another published vocabulary, so that there is a stable URI that can be added to the `@context`.

15.5.1 Choosing URIs for ad hoc terms

For projects that have their own web-presence, URIs MAY be defined there and SHOULD resolve to useful content. For example, for a project with web page `https://example.com/some-project` the property `myProperty` could have a URI: `https://example.com/some-project/terms#myProperty` which resolves to an HTML page that explains each term using HTML anchors:

```
<section id="myProperty">
  <h2>Property: myProperty</h2>
  <dl><dt>Permalink:</dt>
    <dd>https://example.com/some-project/terms#myProperty</dd>
  </dl>
  <p>Description of property ...
</p>
</section>
```

Tip: Ensure you have a consistent use of `http` or `https` (preferring `https`) as well as consistent path `/vocab` vs `/vocab/` vs `/vocab/index.html` (preferring the shortest that is also visible in browser).

For ad hoc terms where the crate author does not have the resources to create and maintain an HTML page, authors may use the RO-Crate public namespace (`https://w3id.org/ro/terms/`) to reserve their terms. For example, an ad-hoc URI MAY be used in the form `https://w3id.org/ro/terms/some-project#myProperty` where `some-project` is acting as a *namespace* for one or more related terms like `education`. Ad-hoc namespaces under `https://w3id.org/ro/terms/` are available on first-come-first-serve basis; to avoid clashes, namespaces SHOULD be registered by submitting terms and definitions to the RO-Crate terms project.

In both cases, to use an ad-hoc term in an RO-Crate, the URI MUST be included in the local context:

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
    {"education": "https://example.com/some-project/terms#education",
     "interests": "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/some-project#interests"},
  ],
  "@graph": [ ... ]
}
```

15.5.2 Add local definitions of ad hoc terms

Following the conventions used by Schema.org, ad-hoc terms SHOULD also include definitions in the RO-Crate with at minimum:

- `@id` is an absolute URI (see choosing)
- `@type` of `DefinedTerm`, `rdf:Property` or `rdfs:Class`. Use `rdf:Property` for terms that can be used as JSON-LD keys (after being mapped by the context), or `rdfs:Class` for terms that can be used with `@type`. Use `DefinedTerm` for any other defined concepts that will be referenced by `@id`, e.g. from `creativeWorkStatus`.
- `name` with the human readable version of the term, e.g. `http://example.com/vocab#makesFood` has label `"makes food"`
- `description` documenting and clarifying the meaning of the term. For instance the term `education` meaning *Person's education level, e.g. primary school* (compared to the meaning *Educational Material*)

```
{
  "@id": "http://purl.archive.org/textcommons/terms#participant",
  "@type": "DefinedTerm",
  "name": "participant",
  "description": "This role is intended for minor participants such as audience members"
}
```

Tip: It is **not** a requirement to use English for the terms, labels or comments.

More information about the relationship of this term to other terms MAY be provided using `domainIncludes`, `rangeIncludes`, `rdfs:subClassOf`, `rdfs:subPropertyOf`, `sameAs` following the conventions used in the Schema.org schema – “*Schema.org style schemas*”. For compatibility with RDFS/OWL tools, `name` and `description` SHOULD be duplicated using the RDFS properties `rdfs:label` and `rdfs:comment`:

```
{
  "@id": "http://purl.archive.org/textcommons/terms#participant",
  "@type": "rdf:Property",
  "name": "participant",
  "rdfs:label": "participant",
  "description": "This role is intended for minor participants such as audience members",
  "rdfs:comment": "This role is intended for minor participants such as audience members",
  "rdfs:subPropertyOf": {"@id": "http://schema.org/participant"},
  "domainIncludes": {"@id": "http://schema.org/CreativeWork"},
  "rangeIncludes": [
    {"@id": "http://schema.org/Person"},
    {"@id": "http://schema.org/Organization"}
  ],
  "sameAs": "http://www.language-archives.org/REC/role.html#participant",
}
```

Note: Schema.org also provides the types `Class` and `Property`. These MAY be used as an additional `@type` corresponding to `rdfs:Class` and `rdf:Property`, but as these are (for some reason) not used in Schema.org style schemas, they are also not required by RO-Crate. Likewise, an ontology defining such

terms externally may be declaring properties there with more specific types like `owl:ObjectProperty` which do not need to be reflected in the RO-Crate reference.

Tip: For compatibility with the official schema.org JSON-LD context, make sure any referenced `@id` to schema.org terms starts with `http://` rather than `https://` as shown in the browser.

15.6 Grouping extensions as an RO-Crate profile

If several RO-Crates are using the same `@context` extension terms, or define the same additional ad-hoc terms, then it may make sense to specify these within an RO-Crate profile that the crates can then explicitly declare conformance to.

The `@id` of the extension terms should after the move be made absolute URIs that resolve to the profile crate – if these were made using `https://w3id.org/ro/terms/` then a request to set up such redirects can be made.

For terms it is RECOMMENDED to change the `@id` of the terms after moving to be based on the profile's permalink, e.g. the profile with `@id https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate` defines the term `https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#CPMProvenanceFile`.

See sections on profile extension terms and Profile JSON-LD context. Custom file formats and common contextual entities may also be moved to the profile, ensuring their `@id` are absolute URI and resolve to the profile JSON-LD.

This can reduce repetition in their JSON-LD, but means additional measures must be taken to ensure the resulting RO-Crates remain functional over time, e.g. not to remove terms as the profile evolves over time.

Example:

```
{ "@context": [
  "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context",
  "https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate/0.1"
],
"@graph": [
  {
    "@type": "CreativeWork",
    "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
    "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1"},
    "about": {"@id": "./"}
  },
  {
    "@id": "./",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/cpm/crate/0.1"},
    "hasPart": [
      { "@id": "CPM_COMPLIANT_PROVENANCE" }
    ],
    "...": ""
  }
]
```

```

},
{
  "@id": "CPM_COMPLIANT_PROVENANCE",
  "@type": ["File", "CPMProvenanceFile"],
  "encodingFormat": [
    "text/provenance-notation",
    { "@id": "http://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-n-20130430/" }
  ],
  "name": "Provenance file"
}
]
}

```

In the example above, the type `CPMProvenanceFile` is resolved to `https://w3id.org/cpm/ro-crate#CPMProvenanceFile` by the matching key in the second `@context` when content-negotiating for `application/ld+json` (browsers may see the human-readable documentations).

The contextual entity `http://www.w3.org/TR/2013/REC-prov-n-20130430/` for `encodingFormat` is defined within the profile rather than in this specific crate, however in this example that `@id` resolves to the textual specification at W3C rather than back to the Profile Crate.

16 APPENDIX: Handling relative URI references

In an *Attached RO-Crate Package*, the *RO-Crate Metadata File* use *relative URI references* to identify files and directories contained within the *RO-Crate Root* and its children. As described in section *Describing entities in JSON-LD*, relative URI references are also frequently used for identifying *Contextual entities*.

16.1 Converting from Attached to Detached RO-Crate Package

An *Attached RO-Crate Package* can be published on the Web by placing its *RO-Crate Root* directory on a static file-based Web server (e.g. Nginx, Apache HTTPd, GitHub Pages). The use of relative URI references in the *RO-Crate Metadata File* ensures identifiers of data entities work as they should.

Sometimes it is desired to make a *Detached RO-Crate Package*, e.g. for depositing or integrating the *RO-Crate Metadata File* into a knowledge graph or repository that is unable to preserve data files using their existing pathnames. In this case one needs to:

1. Decide on new Web locations for individual data files and update their absolute URI in `@id`
2. Observe the preservation considerations for Web-based Data Entities
3. Ensure all nested directories not browsable on the Web are represented as `Dataset` with its content listed with `hasPart` or `distribution` (see

section Directories on the web). Change their relative @id to become absolute, e.g. using ARCP.

4. Rewrite the JSON-LD with absolute URIs for data entities

If the RO-Crate is already published on the Web, with directory browsing enabled for nested directories, then these steps can be achieved using JSON-LD tooling.

For example, as the RO-Crate Metadata file <https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.json> along with the RO-Crate Root is published on the Web (using GitHub Pages), we can generate a random UUID (e.g. `d6be5c9b-132a-4a93-9837-3e02e06c08e6`) and use JSON-LD flattening from this context:

```
{ "@context": [
  {"@base": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.json"},
  "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context"
]
```

to this context:

```
{ "@context": [
  {"@base": "arcp://uuid,d6be5c9b-132a-4a93-9837-3e02e06c08e6/"},
  "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context"
]
```

None of the existing resources will have a @id starting with this fresh base URI, therefore all URIs will be made absolute. The resulting {@base: ..} is harmless, but can be removed from the output JSON-LD.

Example output (abbreviated):

```
{
  "@context": [
    {"@base": "arcp://uuid,d6be5c9b-132a-4a93-9837-3e02e06c08e6/"},
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context"
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1"},
      "about": {"@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/"},
      "creator": {"@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9842-9718"}
    },
    {
      "@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "hasPart": [
        {"@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/index.html"},
        {"@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/example/"},
      ],
    }
  ],
}
```

```

    "name": "Workflow RO-Crate profile"
  },
  ...
]
}

```

Identifiers like `ro-crate-metadata.json`, `./`, `index.html` and `example/` have been translated to absolute URIs. However, even in detached RO-Crates, the RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor is required to have an `@id` of `ro-crate-metadata.json`, so this needs to be manually changed to the required value. The full URI can be provided by adding a `contentUrl` that points to it:

```

{
  "@context": [
    {"@base": "arcp://uuid,d6be5c9b-132a-4a93-9837-3e02e06c08e6/"},
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context"
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1"},
      "about": {"@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/"},
      "contentUrl": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "creator": {"@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9842-9718"}
    },
    ...
  ]
}

```

The above JSON-LD processing will also expand any #-based local identifiers of contextual entities:

```

{
  "@id": "https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.json#include-main-workflow",
  "@type": "Recommendation",
  "category": "MUST",
  "name": "Include Main Workflow",
  "itemReviewed": {
    "@id": "https://bioschemas.org/ComputationalWorkflow"
  }
}

```

In this approach, the Detached RO-Crate Package can be resolved to the corresponding Attached RO-Crate Package by following the `@id` of the Root Data Set.

If the new Detached RO-Crate Package is not meant as a snapshot of the corresponding Attached RO-Crate Package, then such contextual entities should be assigned new `@id`, e.g. by generating random UUIDs like `urn:uuid:e47e41d9-f924-4c07-bc90-97e7ed34fe35`. Such transformations

are typically not catered for by traditional JSON-LD tooling and require additional implementation.

16.2 Converting from Detached to Attached RO-Crate Package

Converting a Detached Crate to an Attached Crate can mean multiple things depending on intentions, and may imply an elaborate process.

First, check if the Root Data Entity already have a distribution download listed, in which case that can be retrieved as the corresponding Attached Crate.

To archive a snapshot of an Detached Crate's metadata, keeping all data entities web-based:

- Create a new folder as the *RO-Crate Root*, save the *RO-Crate Metadata Document* as the *RO-Crate Metadata File* according to Attached RO-Crate Package structure
- Copy the absolute `@id` to become an `identifier` according to recommendations for Root Data Entity identifier
- Optional: Change the `@id` of the Root Data Entity to `./` and update all references to it, including from the Metadata Descriptor

If the new Attached Crate is intended as a *fork* that will evolve independently of the Detached Crate, then:

- Delete the `identifier`, add the previous `@id` as `isBasedOn`
- Delete/update `datePublished` and `publisher`
- Add yourself as `author` or `contributor` to the Root Data Entity
- Add records of changes to the Crate

To additionally save Web-based Data entities to become part of the Detached Crate, a possible algorithm is:

- For each data entity which `@type` include `Dataset`:
 - If it has a distribution download, retrieve and unpack that according to its `encodingFormat`, using its new folder name as the new local path name.
 - If not, create a corresponding folder in the *RO-Crate Root*, possibly generating the local path name based on `name` or path elements of `@id` URI
 - Replace the `@id` of the dataset and all its references with the *relative URI* based on the path from the RO-Crate Root, encoding file paths as necessary.
 - Recurse this algorithm to process each data entity from this dataset's `hasPart`
- For each data entity which `@type` include `File`:
 - Decide based on `@id` URI elements, `contentSize` `encodingFormat` and (possibly implied) `licence` if this file is acceptable to archive
 - Retrieve the file and check the `contentSize` matches, if specified
 - Store the file.
 - * If the file has a `localPath` property, use that relative to the *RO-Crate Root*.

- * If not, calculate a path from the folder of the first `Dataset` that directly has this data entity as its `hasPart`.
- Add the previous `@id` downloaded from as `contentUrl` according to Data entities in an Attached RO-Crate that are also on the Web
- Replace the `@id` of the `File` with the *relative URI* based on the path from the RO-Crate Root, encoding file paths as necessary.

As this procedure can be error-prone (e.g. a Web-based entity may not be accessible or may require authentication), the implementation should consider the new *Attached RO-Crate Package* as a *fork* and update `identifier` and `isDefinedBy` as specified above.

Tip: If you are archiving an Attached RO-Crate Package that is already on the Web, then first establish the absolute URI for the root, and retrieve all payload files that are considered URI path-wise to be part the RO-Crate Root, creating corresponding local paths. In this scenario the above algorithm can be simplified and the rewriting of identifiers can be avoided if they are already relative URIs.

16.3 Handling relative URI references when using JSON-LD/RDF tools

When using JSON-LD tooling and RDF libraries to consume or generate RO-Crates, extra care should be taken to ensure these URI references are handled correctly.

For this, a couple of scenarios are sketched below with recommendations for consistent handling:

16.4 Flattening JSON-LD from nested JSON

If performing JSON-LD flattening to generate a valid *RO-Crate Metadata File* for a *Attached RO-Crate Package*, add `@base: null` to the input JSON-LD `@context` array to avoid expanding relative URI references. The flattening `@context` SHOULD NOT need `@base: null`.

Example, this JSON-LD is in compacted form which may be beneficial for processing, but is not yet valid *RO-Crate Metadata File* as it has not been flattened into a `@graph` array.

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context"
  ],
  "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
  "@type": "CreativeWork",
  "description": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)",
  "conformsTo": {"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"},
  "about": {
    "@id": "./",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "name": "Example RO-Crate",
  }
}
```

```

    "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
    "hasPart": [
      { "@id": "data1.txt",
        "@type": "File",
        "description": "One of hopefully many Data Entities",
      },
      { "@id": "subfolder/",
        "@type": "Dataset"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Performing JSON-LD flattening with:

```

{ "@context":
  "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context"
}

```

Results in a valid *RO-Crate JSON-LD* (actual order in `@graph` may differ):

```

{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
      },
      "about": {
        "@id": "./"
      },
      "description": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)"
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
      "hasPart": [
        {
          "@id": "data1.txt"
        },
        {
          "@id": "subfolder/"
        }
      ],
      "name": "Example RO-Crate"
    },
    {
      "@id": "data1.txt",
      "@type": "File",
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    "description": "One of hopefully many Data Entities"
  },
  {
    "@id": "subfolder/",
    "@type": "Dataset"
  }
]
}

```

Note: The saved *RO-Crate JSON-LD* SHOULD NOT include `{@base: null}` in its `@context`.

16.5 Expanding/parsing JSON-LD keeping relative referencing

JSON-LD Expansion can be used to resolve terms from the `@context` to absolute URIs, e.g. `http://schema.org/description`. This may be needed to parse extended properties or for combinations with other Linked Data.

This algorithm would normally also expand `@id` fields based on the current base URI of the *RO-Crate Metadata File*, but this may be a temporary location like `file:///tmp/rocrate54/ro-crate-metadata.json`, meaning `@id: subfolder/` becomes `file:///tmp/rocrate54/subfolder/` after JSON-LD expansion.

To avoid absoluting local identifiers, before expanding, augment the JSON-LD `@context` to ensure it is an array that includes `{"@base": null}`.

For example, expanding this JSON-LD:

```

{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
    {"@base": null}
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
      },
      "about": {
        "@id": "./"
      },
      "description": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)"
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
      "hasPart": [

```

```

    {
      "@id": "data1.txt"
    },
    {
      "@id": "subfolder/"
    }
  ],
  "name": "Example RO-Crate"
}
]
}

```

Results in a expanded form without `@context`, using absolute URIs for properties and types, but retains relative URI references for entities within the *RO-Crate Root*:

```

[
  {
    "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
    "@type": [
      "http://schema.org/CreativeWork"
    ],
    "http://schema.org/about": [
      {
        "@id": "./"
      }
    ],
    "http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo": [
      {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
      }
    ],
    "http://schema.org/description": [
      {
        "@value": "RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor (this file)"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "@id": "./",
    "@type": [
      "http://schema.org/Dataset"
    ],
    "http://schema.org/description": [
      {
        "@value": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity"
      }
    ],
    "http://schema.org/hasPart": [
      {
        "@id": "data1.txt"
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

```

    },
    {
      "@id": "subfolder/"
    }
  ],
  "http://schema.org/name": [
    {
      "@value": "Example RO-Crate"
    }
  ]
}
]

```

Note: `@base`: `null` will not relativize existing absolute URIs that happen to be contained by the *RO-Crate Root* (see section Relativizing absolute URIs within RO-Crate Root).

Tip: Most RDF parsers supporting JSON-LD will perform this kind of expansion before generating triples, but not all RDF stores or serializations support relative URI references. Consider using an alternative `@base` as detailed in sections below.

16.6 Establishing absolute URI for RO-Crate Root

When loading *RO-Crate JSON-LD* as RDF, or combining the crate's Linked Data into a larger JSON-LD, it is important to ensure correct base URI to resolve URI references that are relative to the *RO-Crate Root*.

Note: When retrieving an RO-Crate over the web, servers might have performed HTTP redirections so that the base URI is different from what was requested. It is RECOMMENDED to follow section Establishing a Base URI of RFC3986 before resolving relative links from the *RO-Crate Metadata File*.

For instance, consider this HTTP redirection from a permalink (simplified):

```
GET https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.0/crate HTTP/1.1
```

```
HTTP/1.1 301 Moved Permanently
```

```
Location: https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.jsonld
```

```
GET https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.0/ro-crate-metadata.jsonld HTTP/1.1
```

```
HTTP/1.1 200 OK
```

```
Content-Type: application/ld+json
```

```

{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.0/context",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.jsonld",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.0"
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

```

    },
    "about": {
      "@id": "./"
    },
    "license": {
      "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/"
    }
  },
  {
    "@id": "./",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "hasPart": [
      {
        "@id": "index.html"
      }
    ]
  }
]
}

```

Following redirection we see that:

- *Base URI* of the *RO-Crate Metadata File* becomes `https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.0/`
- The absolute URI for `index.html` resolves to `https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.0/index.html`
 - ..rather than `https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.0/index.html` which would not redirect correctly

This example also use RO-Crate 1.0, where the *RO-Crate Metadata File* is called `ro-crate-metadata.jsonld` instead of `ro-crate-metadata.json`. Note that the recommended algorithm to find the Root Data Entity is agnostic to the actual filename.

16.7 Finding RO-Crate Root in RDF triple stores

When parsing *RO-Crate JSON-LD* as RDF, where the RDF framework performs resolution to absolute URIs, it may be difficult to find the *RO-Crate Root* in the parsed triples.

The algorithm proposed in section Root Data Entity allows finding the RDF resource describing `ro-crate-metadata.json`, independent of its parsed base URI. We can adopt this for RDF triples, thus finding crates conforming to this specification can be queried with SPARQL:

```
PREFIX schema: <http://schema.org/>
```

```

SELECT ?crate ?metadatafile
WHERE {
  ?crate      a                schema:Dataset .
  ?metadatafile schema:about  ?crate .
  filter(contains(str(?metadatafile), "ro-crate-metadata.json"))
}

```

Note: The query above will find *all* Root Data Entities in the RDF graph. This is useful when querying RDF triple stores which contain many RO-Crates, but

it also means that multiple results could be returned when the query is used on single RO-Crates which contain other nested or referenced RO-Crates.

16.8 Parsing as RDF with a different RO-Crate Root

When parsing a *RO-Crate Metadata File* into RDF triples, for instance uploading it to a *graph store* like Apache Jena's Fuseki, it is important to ensure consistent *base URI*:

- Some RDF stores and RDF formats don't support relative URI references in triples (see RDF 1.1 note on IRIs)
- The *RO-Crate Root* may depend on where the *RO-Crate Metadata File* was parsed from, e.g. `<file:///tmp/ro-crate-metadata.json>` (file) or `<http://localhost:3030/test/ro-crate-metadata.json>` (web upload)
- Parsing multiple RO-Crates into the same RDF graph, using same base URI, may merge them into the same RO-Crate
- `ro-crate-metadata.json` may not be recognized as JSON-LD and must be renamed to `ro-crate-metadata.jsonld`
- Web servers hosting `ro-crate-metadata.json` may not send the JSON-LD *Content-Type*
- If base URI is not correct it may be difficult to find the corresponding file and directory paths from an RDF query returning absolute URIs

Tip: If the RDF library can parse the *RO-Crate JSON-LD* directly by retrieving from a `http/https` URI of the *RO-Crate Metadata File* it should calculate the correct base URI as detailed in section Establishing absolute URI for RO-Crate Root and you should **not** need to override the base URI as detailed here.

If a web-based URI for the *RO-Crate root* is known, then this can be supplied as a *base URI*. Most RDF tools support a `--base` option or similar. If this is not possible, then the `@context` of the RO-Crate JSON-LD can be modified by ensuring the `@context` is an array that sets the desired `@base`:

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
    {"@base": "http://example.com/crate255/"}
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
      },
      "about": {
        "@id": "./"
      }
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
```

```

    "@type": "Dataset",
    "name": "Example RO-Crate",
    "hasPart": [
      {
        "@id": "data1.txt"
      },
      {
        "@id": "subfolder/"
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "@id": "data1.txt",
    "@type": "File",
    "description": "One of hopefully many Data Entities"
  },
  {
    "@id": "subfolder/",
    "@type": "Dataset"
  }
]
}

```

Parsing this will generate triples like below using `http://example.com/crate255/` as the *RO-Crate Root* (shortened):

```

<http://example.com/crate255/ro-crate-metadata.json>
  <http://purl.org/dc/terms/conformsTo>
    <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3> .

```

```

<http://example.com/crate255/ro-crate-metadata.json>
  <http://schema.org/about>
    <http://example.com/crate255/> .

```

```

<http://example.com/crate255/>
  <http://schema.org/name>
    "Example RO-Crate" .

```

```

<http://example.com/crate255/>
  <http://schema.org/hasPart>
    <http://example.com/crate255/data1.txt> .

```

```

<http://example.com/crate255/>
  <http://schema.org/hasPart>
    <http://example.com/crate255/subfolder/> .

```

```

<http://example.com/crate255/data1.txt>
  <http://schema.org/description>
    "One of hopefully many Data Entities" .

```

Generating a *RO-Crate JSON-LD* from such triples can be done by first finding

the RO-Crate Root and then use it as base URI to relativize absolute URIs within RO-Crate Root.

16.9 Establishing a base URI inside a ZIP file

An RO-Crate may have been packaged as a ZIP file or similar archive. RO-Crates may exist in a temporary file path which should not determine its identifiers.

When parsing such crates it is recommended to use the Archive and Package (arcp) URI scheme to establish a temporary/location-based UUID or hash-based (SHA256) *base URI*.

For instance, given a randomly generated UUID `b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065` we can use `arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/` as the `@base`:

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3/context",
    {"@base": "arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/"}
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
      },
      "about": {
        "@id": "./"
      }
    },
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
      "hasPart": [
        {
          "@id": "data1.txt"
        },
        {
          "@id": "subfolder/"
        }
      ],
      "name": "Example RO-Crate"
    },
    {
      "@id": "data1.txt",
      "@type": "File",
      "description": "One of hopefully many Data Entities"
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    },
    {
      "@id": "subfolder/",
      "@type": "Dataset"
    }
  ]
}

```

Parsing this as RDF will generate triples including:

```

<arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/ro-crate-metadata.json>
  <http://schema.org/about>
    <arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/> .

<arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/>
  <http://schema.org/hasPart>
    <arcp://uuid,b7749d0b-0e47-5fc4-999d-f154abe68065/data1.txt> .

```

Here consumers can assume / is the *RO-Crate Root* and generating relative URIs can safely be achieved by search-replace as the arcp URI is unique. Saving *RO-Crate JSON-LD* from the triples can be done by using the arcp URI to relativize absolute URIs within RO-Crate Root.

Tip: BagIt: The arcp specification suggests how BagIt identifiers can be used to calculate the base URI. See also section Combining with other packaging schemes - note that in this approach the *RO-Crate Root* will be the payload folder /data/ under the calculated arcp base URI.

16.10 Relativizing absolute URIs within RO-Crate Root

Some applications may prefer working with absolute URIs, e.g. in a joint graph store or web-based repository, but should relativize URIs within the *RO-Crate Root* before generating the *RO-Crate Metadata File*.

Assuming a repository at `example.com` has JSON-LD with absolute URIs:

```

{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3",
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "http://example.com/crate415/ro-crate-metadata.json",
      "@type": "CreativeWork",
      "conformsTo": {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
      },
      "about": {
        "@id": "http://example.com/crate415/"
      },
    },
  ],
  {
    "@id": "http://example.com/crate415/",
    "@type": "Dataset",
    "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
  },
}

```

```

    "hasPart": [
      {
        "@id": "http://example.com/crate415/data1.txt"
      },
      {
        "@id": "http://example.com/crate415/subfolder/"
      }
    ],
    "name": "Example RO-Crate"
  }
]
}

```

Then performing JSON-LD flattening with this @context:

```

{ "@context": [
  { "@base": "http://example.com/crate415/" },
  "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
]
}

```

Will output *RO-Crate JSON-LD* with relative URIs:

```

{
  "@context": [
    {
      "@base": "http://example.com/crate415/"
    },
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
  ],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": "Dataset",
      "description": "The RO-Crate Root Data Entity",
      "hasPart": [
        {
          "@id": "data1.txt"
        },
        {
          "@id": "subfolder/"
        }
      ]
    },
    {
      "name": "Example RO-Crate"
    }
  ],
  {
    "@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
    "@type": "CreativeWork",
    "conformsTo": {
      "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.3"
    }
  },
  {
    "about": {

```

```

    "id": "./"
  }
}
]
}

```

Warning :This method would also relativize URIs outside the *RO-Crate Root* that are on the same host, e.g. `http://example.com/crate255/other.txt` would become `../create255/other.txt` - this can particularly be a challenge with local `file:///` URIs. ‘

17 APPENDIX: Changelog

- RO-Crate 1.3.0
 - **Notable change:** Updated the Bioschemas namespace to `https://bioschemas.org/terms/` for all types and properties (previously `https://bioschemas.org/` for types and `https://bioschemas.org/properties` for properties). This change affects 4 terms in the JSON-LD context: `ComputationalWorkflow`, `FormalParameter`, `input`, and `output`. This is primarily relevant to those describing workflows with RO-Crate, either using the Workflows and Scripts chapter or the Workflow RO-Crate profile and its derivatives. #529

Term	Previous URI	New URI
ComputationalWorkflow	https://bioschemas.org/ComputationalWorkflow	<code>https://bioschemas.org/terms/ComputationalWorkflow</code>
FormalParameter	https://bioschemas.org/FormalParameter	<code>https://bioschemas.org/terms/FormalParameter</code>
input	https://bioschemas.org/properties/input	<code>https://bioschemas.org/terms/input</code>
output	https://bioschemas.org/properties/output	<code>https://bioschemas.org/terms/output</code>

- Update schema.org to v30.0. This update adds many new terms and removes none. None of the new terms are used in the 1.3 specification. Some of them may however be of interest to profile creators, including `AuthenticateAction`, `Certification`, `Credential`, `Error`, `InstantaneousEvent`, `LoginAction`, `OperatingSystem`, `RuntimePlatform`, pronouns, various types of source for digital objects to be used with `digitalSourceType`, and other properties associated with the classes above.
- All other changes listed below are minor and are also applied to the web version of RO-Crate 1.2.
- Fix error in appendix section Converting from Attached to Detached RO-Crate Package; the metadata descriptor must be `ro-crate-metadata.json` and should not be converted to an absolute path. `ro-crate#538` #524
- Add relevant missing `rdfs:` properties to core RO-Crate Profile `Crate` #471
- Fix typos & incorrect links #169, #527
- Improve page metadata for better previews/SEO (no content changed) #499

- RO-Crate 1.2.0 <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.2>
 - Clarified that the RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor MUST have `@id` of `ro-crate-metadata.json` by removing conflicting statements elsewhere in the specification #365
 - Updated the Bioschemas namespace for properties from <https://bioschemas.org/Computational> to <https://bioschemas.org/properties/>. This change affects only the `input` and `output` properties in the JSON-LD context.
 - **Change:** Replaced name-based algorithm for finding root #198 #365
 - Updated algorithm to always use string filter to find root #189 #421 (see algorithm)
 - **Change:** Files on the web should now use `contentUrl` for direct download #259

 - Clarify entity terminology and when File/Dataset entities are and are not data entities #204 #426
 - Update JSON-LD context to schema.org 22.0. Note that upstream adds >230 terms, and removed terms `AuthenticContent`, `MissingContext`, `constrainingProperty` (now `constraintProperty`), `measuredValue`, `observedNode` . #263 #274
 - Remove custom mapping of `funding` for Bioschemas (now officially <http://schema.org/funding>)
 - Added `localPath` to JSON-LD context (<https://w3id.org/ro/terms#localPath>) and described its use in web-based entities #406 #390
 - Updated for ComputationalWorkflow 1.0 profile #185
 - Clarified Directories on the web format is a media type, not extension #205

 - **New:** Extended introduction with a running example #227 #215 #219 – see also RO-Crate tutorials.
 - **New:** Added section Profiles and the concept *Profile Crate* #250 #251 #255 #256 #407
 - Define terms for Profiles #248
 - Added subsection for grouping extensions in a profile #233 #233
 - Allow more types on root #182 #223
 - Added subsection on root data entity identifier #183
 - **New:** Introduces distinction of Attached/Detached RO-Crate #248 #189 #183 #390 #405
 - Included Attached/Detached RO-Crate in terminology #248
 - Rephrased description of payload files #183 #189
 - Describes `ro-crate-preview.html` as entity #106 #210
 - Added usage of `DefinedTerm`; `rdfs:label` and `comment` optional; replaced example #232 #208 #106
 - Added section on converting Attached/Detached RO-Crates #189
 - Added Common principles for RO-Crate entities #225 #260 #404
 - Added note on ELN (Electronic Lab Notebook) implementation to appendix section on combining with other packaging schemes #389
 - Clarified mandatory metadata for the Root Data Entity #404
 - Many sections reviewed to improve language and examples #378 #382 #404 #410 #411 #412 #413 #414 #415 #418 #425

- RO-Crate 1.1.2
 - Typo fixes in data entity section #177, workflow section #180, meta-data section #181
 - Correct namespace for `rdfs:comment` on ad-hoc terms #164
 - Fixed broken links to Bioschemas and SPAR ontologies #185 (note: `conformsTo` URIs unchanged, will be updated in RO-Crate 1.2)
- RO-Crate 1.1.1
 - Introduction highlight not all Data entities are files #125 #127
- RO-Crate 1.1.0 <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1>
 - **Note:** The RO-Crate metadata file is renamed to `ro-crate-metadata.json` to facilitate use of JSON editors. #82 #84
 - Data entities can reference external resources with absolute URI #74
 - Added section on considerations for Web-based Data Entities #74
 - The Root Data Entity is no longer required to be `./` #74
 - RO-Crate Root directory no longer requires payload files #74
 - Workflows and scripts section now aligned with BioSchemas ComputationalWorkflow profile #81 #100
 - Added section Programming with JSON-LD and note that `@type` might be an array #85
 - Added new section Handling relative URI references #73
 - JSON-LD context no longer sets `@base: null` #73
 - Added note on Encoding file paths #77 #80
 - Added section Choosing URLs for ad hoc terms #71 #90
 - Section RO-Crate JSON-LD Media type expanded to suggest HTTP server configuration
 - Update JSON-LD context to Schema.org 10.0
 - Remove HTML use of `relatedLink` property in RepositoryCollection example #91
 - Distinguish between contextual/data entities #94
 - RO-Crate preview HTML no longer needs to “contain same information as JSON-LD” #108
 - Change theme to `jekyll-rtd-theme` and split into multiple pages #95
 - Fixed typos in JSON and English
 - Additional metadata standards showed wrong PCDM namespace #112
 - Citation example expanded 12a6754
 - Terminology adds property, type, entity cc10e28
 - In People `author` can also be applied to `CreativeWork` e086b8b
 - Provenance section on Software-used now points to Workflows section (and vice versa) 5d89872 40de6c7
 - In JSON-LD appendix `@id` should not include `./` 74ef6f1
 - Several sections reviewed to improve language and examples #91 #92 #93 #94 #96 #97 #98 #101 #102 #103 #104 #105 #111 #114
- RO-Crate 1.0.1
 - Fix JSON typo in example
- RO-Crate 1.0.0 <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.0>
 - Description of RO-Crate Metadata File now required

- * .. must use `conformsTo` to indicate RO-Crate version
 - Clarified use of RO-Crate JSON-LD Context
 - Linked Data principles added
 - RO-Crate JSON-LD Context updated to use Schema.org 5.0
 - Workflow and Script now typed with `@type` array instead of `additionalType`
 - Simplified tables of direct properties to list of properties
 - Simplified example of `affiliation`
 - Clarified `#identifiers` and `_:identifiers`
 - Removed links to data.research.uts.edu.au examples
 - Added licensing of metadata
 - Expanded on *Equipment used to create files*
 - Simplified Workflow and Script section
 - Added appendix on JSON-LD
 - Added BagIt implementation notes
 - Added Repository-specific identifiers
 - RO-Crate JSON-LD now licensed CC0
 - RO-Crate JSON-LD self-identifies its version
- RO-Crate 0.2.1
 - Added DOI and document metadata
- RO-Crate 0.2.0 <https://w3id.org/ro/crate/0.2>
 - Based on two earlier specifications:
 - * RO Lite 0.1.0
 - * DataCrate Specification version 1.0.0 2019-04-12
 - RO-Crate Metadata file has been renamed to `ro-crate-metadata.jsonld` instead of `CATALOG.json` (DataCrate) or `manifest.jsonld` (RO-Lite)
 - RO Crate Website renamed to `ro-crate-metadata.html` instead of DataCrate’s `CATALOG.html`
 - “RO-Lite” and “DataCrate” renamed to “RO-Crate”
 - Multiple examples and clarifications added
 - RO-Crate directory no longer requires BagIt structure
 - Added section on Workflows and scripts
 - RO-Crate Metadata File must describe itself as being about the RO-Crate Dataset.
 - JSON-LD should now be flattened and then compacted (RO-Lite allowed any JSON-LD, DataCrate required flattened)

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